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Strengthening Self-Reliance: TVET and Skills Education for Youth in Jordan

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

Executive summary	5
Introduction	8
Background	8
About the research	9
Research Objectives	9
Methodology	10
Research design	10
Limitations	12
SECTION I: Yemeni, Somali, and Sudanese asylum seekers and refugees in Jordan	13
I.1 Overview of key areas of vulnerabilities	13
I.1.1 Legal status and documentation	13
I.1.2 Livelihoods, income & indebtedness	15
I.1.3 Education	16
SECTION II: Technical and vocational education and training in Jordan	17
II.1 Overview of TVET and skills	17
II.2 Current TVET and skills strategy	18
II.3 Challenges of the Jordanian TVET system	18
II.4 Initiatives to enhance TVET system in Jordan	20
II.5 TVET and skills for refugees in Jordan	22
SECTION III: TVET and Skills for Yemeni, Somali and Sudanese ASR in Jordan	25
III.1 Availability of TVET and skills training	25
III.2 Accessibility to TVET and skills training	27
III.2.1 Legal barriers and documentation	27
III.2.2 Fees and funding opportunities	27
III.3 Acceptability of TVET and skills training	28
III.3.1 TVET and skills preferences among refugees	28
III.3.2 Quality of TVET	31
III.3.3 Suitability of TVET for refugees' needs and realities	32
SECTION V: The way forward	36
V.1 Key advocacy messages	36
V.2 Recommendations	36
References	39
Annex I: Donor mapping of TVET and Skills funded projects for fostering livelihood for refugees in Jordan (2015 – 2025)	41

List of abbreviations

ARDD	Arab Renaissance for Democracy and Development
AS/R	Asylum Seekers and Refugees
BAU	Balqa Applied University
BMZ	Ministry for Economic Cooperation and Development of the Federal Republic of Germany
CRP	Collateral Repair Project
EU	European Union
ETF	European Bank Training Foundation
FGD	Focus Group Discussion
FCDO	Foreign, Commonwealth and Development Office
GAC	Global Affairs Canada
GIZ	Gemeinschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit
GoJ	Government of Jordan
INGO	International Non-Governmental Organization
JRS	Jesuit Refugee Service
JNQF	Jordanian National Qualifications Framework
KII	Key Informant Interview
KUTC	Khwarizmi University Technical College
MoE	Ministry of Education
MoI	Ministry of Interior
MoL	Ministry of Labor
NET	National Employment and Training Company
SDG	Sustainable Development Goal
TVET	Technical and Vocational Education and Training
TVSDC	Technical and Vocational Skills Development Commission
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
UNHCR	United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees
VAF	Vulnerability Assessment Framework
VHI	Vision Hope International
VTC	Vocational Training Corporation
Investing in the Future	Investing in the Future: Improved educational, social and economic integration of Somali, Sudanese and Yemeni minorities in Jordan

Executive summary

Background

This research has been conducted as part of the “Investing in the Future” initiative, a project implemented by the ARDD in collaboration with VHI, and financially supported by BMZ. By providing various legal services and improved education opportunities, “Investing in the Future” aims to promote inclusive access to quality education for all, ensuring and enhancing the protection of vulnerable individuals and communities in Jordan, particularly, Sudanese, Somali, and Yemeni. According to the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR), Jordan hosts 723,886 registered refugees, from which 12,767 are Yemenis, 4,919 Sudanese, and 468 Somalis. Jordanian authorities and the international aid community have historically overlooked these refugee communities exacerbating their vulnerabilities and needs, including education.

Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) / Skills Education, as stressed by the Global Compact on Refugees and UNHCR’s Education 2030 Strategy, among other international commitments, has been proven to be an efficient educational pathway for refugees to reach durable solutions, as they acquired technical and soft skills that can use in their host country, once they are resettled or in their homeland if they have voluntarily decided to go back.

Research methodology and objectives

This research stems from ARDD’s sponsorship of 15 scholarships to support a three-TVET / Skills program for Sudanese, Somali, and Yemeni refugees, and vulnerable Jordanians, at Khwarizmi University Technical College (KUTC).

Adopting a mixed-methods approach, this research aims to **i)** provide a critical analysis of the Jordanian TVET system, **ii)** analyze the challenges, opportunities, and gaps in TVET and skills for Yemeni, Somali, and Sudanese AS/R in terms of availability, accessibility and acceptability, **iii)** advocate for the educational rights of Sudanese, Somali, and Yemeni refugees in Jordan, and **iv)** implement a protection approach to education by facilitate the learning journey of selected beneficiaries.

Jordanian TVET system: challenges and gaps

- 1. Unimplemented governance framework.** The TVET/Skills governance structure in Jordan is characterized by a high level of fragmentation and inaccuracy in the delimitation of competencies of the stakeholders involved, resulting in overlaps and gaps, lack of accountability, and miscoordination.
- 2. Insufficient coordination among donors,** even TVET/Skills is considered an increasing development priority for many of them.
- 3. Limited funding and inefficient financial strategies.** The public budget adjudicated to TVET / Skills education is limited considering the current needs. Moreover, the Jordanian financial management system governing TVET is not outcomes or performance-based, providing no incentive to public TVET provider to improve their educational services.
- 4. TVET and skills programs are generally not demand but supply-driven,** with private TVET providers performing better in this regard than public ones. Furthermore, soft skills should be considered as essential as technical skills during the design of TVET/Skills curricula.
- 5. Weak engagement with the private sector,** acknowledging the need for stronger public-private partnerships.
- 6. TVET facilities and equipment are not updated and/or adequate,** missing an excellent opportunity to build a more competitive and modern Jordanian workforce.
- 7. TVET trainers and teachers lack the practical experience and pedagogical skills to train new generations.**
- 8. Inclusion.** Although women’s engagement on TVET has progressively increased recently in Jordan, it is still a male-dominated stream. Additionally, TVET opportunities for persons with disabilities are limited.
- 9. Poor social image of TVET among Jordanians.** TVET is only considered an educational option in case of failure in the academic stream.
- 10. Limited transition pathways from the vocational and technical stream to the academic one and vice versa.**
- 11. Limited investment by TVET / Skills providers in career guidance and counseling.**

Key learnings

A) Refugees as TVET students

1. Learning is an individual process.

2. Motivation to enroll in a TVET/Skills program can take many forms: Enhance livelihood opportunities by gaining new technical and soft skills; high interest in the TVET/skills fields students are trained, which makes it crucial to customize such opportunities to their preferences and interests; and TVET as the sole available alternative to traditional academic pathways.

3. Reasons for dropping out of the TVET/Skills training are related to both external (such as getting resettled, health issues, finding a full-time job...) **and internal factors** (such as schedule incompatibility, programs that did not meet students' personal and professional expectations).

4. Transportation challenges can deter refugees from participating in TVET programs, if the TVET provider is located far from their communities.

5. Refugee students consider soft skills as important as technical, particularly, English.

6. Refugee students highly valued the opportunity of paid work experience either during or at the end of their TVET/Skills programs.

7. Education programs for AS/R should benefit from including a protection dimension as part of their design and implementation.

B) TVET and skills programs

1. Flexibility is key to ensuring a successful learning journey, taking into account their training with professional and/or personal obligations.

2. A three-month TVET and skills program was the minimum appropriate duration to provide new skills and knowledge to refugee students.

C) Environment

1. A safe and enabling learning environment is the result of a combination of elements (teachers, equipment, facilities, classmates, staff, curriculum, etc.).

2. Education fosters social cohesion among refugees of different nationalities, and between refugees and host communities.

3. Family and friends' support is crucial for students' educational performance.

4. Undertaking this TVET/Skills program has increased refugee students' social reputation vis à vis their families and communities.

5. Geopolitics affects but does not determine the learning journey of Yemeni, Sudanese, and Somali AS/R. Education is used as a coping mechanism to deal with the regional turmoil.

D) Durable solutions

1. Resettlement is the most preferred durable solution among refugees, and they believe TVET and skills opportunities can speed up this process.

2. Self-reliance as a durable solution for refugees is not possible without inclusive labor market policies. E.g. Further professional sectors open to non-Jordanians, more affordable work permits.

Recommendations

1. Recommendations for donors

- Strengthening the TVET system in Jordan should remain a priority.
- Reach and implement a common donor coordination strategy in the TVET sector in Jordan and identify (or create) a centralized coordination mechanism.
- The protection dimension should be part of the design and implementation of any education program.
- When providing funding to private institutions, encourage the practice of transparency regarding TVET fees by private institutions.

2. Recommendations for CSOs

- Enhance public perceptions of skills and TVET education with public audiences through communication campaigns.
- Promote the vocational and technical stream among women and persons with disabilities.
- Improve referral systems between CSOs and TVET providers.
- Organize periodic information campaigns regarding TVET / Skills opportunities for refugees and Jordanians.
- Engage with TVET and skills providers in offering complementary soft skills programs for refugees.

3. Recommendations for the Private Sector

- Enhance on-the-job training opportunities for TVET and Skills students.
- Support TVET institutions with up-to-date information regarding market needs in terms of skills.
- Engage in national conversations regarding livelihood opportunities in Jordan for non-Jordanians.

4. Recommendations for the GoJ

- Promote multi-stakeholder dialogue for recommendations regarding TVET supply, including private-public partnerships.
- Review the funding strategy of public TVET centers.
- Swift implementation of the current TVET governance structure, including the activation of the work of the TVSDC and improving the coordination among all relevant stakeholders on TVET.
- Re-visit the structure of the current education system for enhanced transition pathways.
- Flexibility for refugees concerning a) documentation requirements, and b) age limits.

5. Recommendation for TVET and Skills providers

- Further investment in career guidance and counseling for the students.
- Incorporate student-centered pedagogical resources into the curriculum to enhance the professional development of teachers.
- Enhance transparency regarding TVET fees by fixing standard rates and publicly disclosing them.
- Include in the TVET/Skills curriculum a paid work experience either during or at the end of the program, whether within the TVET/Skills provider itself (job placement) or externally (private and public companies).
- Further flexibility for refugees in two key areas: a) Choice of the professional field, and b) schedule and attendance requirements.

Introduction

Background

TVET and skills programs have been recognized globally as an effective pathway to provide technical and soft skills to refugees, facilitating their integration into the labor market and promoting self-reliance. Through TVET and skills education, refugees gain marketable skills, enabling them to access employment opportunities, establish businesses, and contribute to the local economy. Additionally, TVET programs offer refugees alternative livelihood options, reducing vulnerability to exploitation and abuse by providing economic independence. Moreover, these programs provide opportunities for personal and professional development, enhancing refugees' self-esteem, confidence, and resilience amidst adversity. Lastly, by equipping refugees with transferable skills, TVET programs support durable solutions by preparing them for eventual return to their home countries, local integration, or resettlement, enabling them to rebuild their lives and contribute to community development upon return.

International commitments regarding TVET and skills for refugees encompass various agreements and strategies. These include the Global Compact for Refugees (2018), Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) 4 and 8 focusing on Quality Education and Decent Work and Economic Growth respectively, as well as UNHCR's Refugee Education 2030 Strategy¹ and the joint pledge "15by30" aims for 15% enrollment of refugee youth in higher education, including TVET, by 2030.²

Regionally, the Regional Refugee & Resilience Plan (3RP) underscores the importance of supporting Syrian refugees in developing their skills through vocational and technical training to meet local job market demands.³ In alignment with the 3RP, the Jordanian Response Plan 2020 - 2022 for the Syria Crisis prioritizes TVET and skills as an educational focus to enhance refugees' livelihoods and self-reliance.

The Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan is home to 723,886 registered refugees, making it the world's second-largest host country for refugees relative to its population. Among them, there are 12,767 Yemenis, 4,919 Sudanese, and 468 Somalis⁴, representing a small fraction of the total refugee population in Jordan, accounting for only 2.5%.

Jordan has committed to various international agreements on education such as the SDG 4⁵, the Global Compact on Refugees⁶, and conventions like the International Covenant on Economic, Social, and Cultural Rights (art. 13), the International Convention on the Rights of the Child (art. 28), and the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) Convention against Discrimination in Education. Despite these commitments, access to quality education remains challenging for refugees in Jordan, particularly for Yemenis, Somalis, and Sudanese.

Despite UNHCR's advocacy of the "One Refugee Approach," Yemeni, Somali, and Sudanese asylum seekers and refugees (AS/R) residing in Jordan still encounter a web of vulnerabilities. These include restricted access to livelihood opportunities, inadequate household incomes, substantial levels of indebtedness, and discrimination rooted in factors such as nationality, race, socioeconomic status, or legal standing. The exclusion of these groups from the 2016 Jordan Compact and subsequent revisions, along with the absence of durable solutions, have exacerbated these challenges.

1 UNHCR, "Refugee Education 2030: A Strategy for Refugee Inclusion" (September 2019), https://reliefweb.int/report/world/refugee-education-2030-strategy-refugee-inclusion?gad_source=1&gclid=Cj0KCQjwiMmwBhDmARIs_ABeQ7xQPZdR09j-CYk5yyBOiE7iV4Nbcq-G96UyWZynexj6z3QTHoWVA_4y0aAn1hEALw_wcB

2 UNHCR, *15by30 Roadmap: Expanding Higher Education, Skills and Self-Reliance for Refugees*, <https://www.unhcr.org/media/15by30-roadmap-expanding-higher-education-skills-and-self-reliance-refugees>

3 UNHCR & UNDP, *3RP Regional Strategic Overview 2024*, (March 2024) https://www.3rpsyriacrisis.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/03/3RP_RSO_2024_.pdf

4 UNHCR, *Registered Refugees and Asylum Seekers in Jordan* (as of 31 March 2024) (April 2024), <https://data.unhcr.org/en/documents/details/108075>

5 "Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all", <https://sdgs.un.org/goals/goal4>

6 Global Compact on Refugees (2018), 26, <https://globalcompactrefugees.org/sites/default/files/2019-12/Global%20compact%20on%20refugees%20EN.pdf>

About the research

This research has been conducted as part of the “Investing in the Future” initiative, a project implemented by ARDD in collaboration with VHI, and financially supported by the Ministry for Economic Cooperation and Development of the Federal Republic of Germany.

“Investing in the Future” is integral to ARDD’s education strategy, pursuing a holistic approach to education. This entails ensuring access to quality education and lifelong learning opportunities for all, which we believe is essential for alleviating poverty, strengthening protection, and enabling lasting positive social transformation and cohesion. Through inclusive education initiatives, the project aims to provide legal services and enhanced educational opportunities for Sudanese, Somali, and Yemeni communities, as well as the Jordanian host population, with the goal of impacting change at individual, community, national, and policy levels.

As part of this endeavor, ARDD has provided funding for 15 scholarships to facilitate a three-month technical and vocational training program at KUTC for Yemeni, Somali, and Sudanese AS/R individuals, as well as vulnerable Jordanians, with the aim of enhancing their livelihood opportunities, and protection manifested in an inclusive quality education.

While education encompasses a broad spectrum, including early childhood development, primary and secondary education, adult literacy, and more, ARDD has chosen to focus on TVET and skills for several reasons:

1. To address the current skills gap among Jordanian youth and the skill demands of the local labor market.
2. TVET is recognized as an efficient and effective pathway to improve livelihood opportunities for refugees.
3. To contribute to the enhancement of the TVET sector in Jordan, aligning with the educational and economic priorities of the Government of Jordan.⁷

The research is structured into four sections: The first section delves into the legal, economic, and educational vulnerabilities faced by Yemeni, Somali, and Sudanese asylum seekers and refugees (AS/R) in Jordan; the second section provides a general overview of the current TVET system in Jordan; the third section focuses on the challenges, opportunities, and gaps in TVET and skills for Yemeni, Somali, and Sudanese AS/R individuals. Lastly, the fourth section outlines the way forward, emphasizing key advocacy messages and offering essential recommendations to donors, civil society organizations (CSOs), the private sector, the Government of Jordan (GoJ), and TVET and skills providers.

Research objectives

The research component of this project has addressed four different objectives, as requested by the project:

- 1 Provide a critical analysis of the TVET system in Jordan.
- 2 Analyze the challenges, opportunities, and gaps on TVET and skills for Yemeni, Somali, and Sudanese AS/R in terms of availability, accessibility and acceptability.
- 3 Advocate for the educational rights of the Yemeni, Somali, and Sudanese AS/R and host communities in Jordan.
- 4 Implement a protection approach to education: Facilitate the learning journey of selected beneficiaries, aged 18 to 28 from Yemeni, Somali, and Sudanese refugee communities in Jordan and vulnerable Jordanians, with technical and vocational / skills training to enhance their livelihood opportunities.

⁷ See Economic Modernisation Vision, National Strategy for Human Resource Development 2016 – 2025, National Employment Strategy 2011-2020, National TVET Strategy 2023-2027.

Methodology

Research design

This research, developed from February 2023 to April 2024, has been conducted applying a **mixed-methods approach**, using predominantly qualitative research methods.

Moreover, it should be noted that this research has adopted a **sectoral approach**, i.e., TVET and skills have been analyzed as part of / sector within education, including a humanitarian analysis dimension considering the subjects of study (Yemeni, Somali, and Sudanese AS/R).

After conducting a thorough desk review regarding the Jordanian TVET system and the legal and socio-economic situation of Yemeni, Somali, and Sudanese AS/R in Jordan, ARDD conducted **6 Focus Group Discussions (FGDs)** with potential beneficiaries – two preliminary FGDs and four structured FGDs. The two preliminary FGDs were organized by legal status (refugees/host communities) to identify common trends and needs within refugee communities, as well as differences between refugees and Jordanians in the dimensions assessed. The remaining four FGDs were organized by the nationalities involved in the project (Yemeni, Somali, Sudanese, Jordanian) to ascertain the differences and similarities each nationality faces in the dimensions evaluated.

- **(Preliminary) FGD 1 (16/03/2023):** Mixed group (female and male 4:4): Jordanian, Yemeni, and Somali (half Jordanian, half refugees: 4:2:2).
- **(Preliminary) FGD 2 (16/03/2023):** Refugee-only mixed group (female and male 4:4): Yemeni, Somali, and Sudanese (3:3:1).
- **(Structured) FGD 3 (26/04/2023):** Refugee-only mixed group (female and male 3:5): Yemeni.
- **(Structured) FGD 4 (26/04/2023):** Refugee-only male group (0:4): Somali.
- **(Structured) FGD 5 (26/04/2023):** Refugee-only mixed group (female and male 2:0): Sudanese.
- **(Structured) FGD 6 (27/04/2023):** Jordanian-only mixed group (female and male 4:5).

These FGDs had two main goals **1)** Gather information among the potential beneficiaries regarding 5 key dimensions (Personal information, educational background, professional experience, motivation, and areas of interest); and **2)** assess the eligibility and suitability of the potential beneficiaries for the TVET / Skills scholarship program.

At the beginning of each FGD, an **individual questionnaire** was distributed to each potential beneficiary. The questionnaire aimed to collect data about their educational background, current occupation situation, and interest and experience on TVET. Jointly with the individual questionnaire, a **technical and soft skill self-assessment** was delivered to each of them to provide ARDD with a sense of self-reported capacities in different technical fields, and individual and collective abilities. The technical skills self-assessment is based on the one designed by the US Department of Labor,⁸ while the soft skills self-assessment is an adaptation of the British Council National Careers Service one.⁹

The information provided by the FGDs, questionnaire and the self-assessments allowed ARDD to design an individual profile for each potential beneficiary. Each profile finalizes with a recommendation regarding the most suitable pathway for the potential beneficiary. Three pathways were identified for the different beneficiaries:

- **Pathway 1:** Youth in situations of vulnerability (mental health, socioeconomic, disabilities...).
- **Pathway 2:** Youth that has recently started a professional career or is willing to start one. Meanwhile, some of them have a clear preference for certain professional fields, others do not, this is the reason why career counseling was recommended as well.
- **Pathway 3:** Promising youth seeking higher education/advanced education opportunities.

Nevertheless, some of the profiles proved to be inconclusive, given that **a)** the potential beneficiaries had identified several work fields in which they would like to work, but they were unclear about which one wants to choose, or **b)** they did not know in what professional sectors they would like to work. Hence, ARDD provided career counseling services for these potential beneficiaries.

⁸ <https://www.careeronestop.org/ExploreCareers/Assessments/self-assessments.aspx>

⁹ <https://nationalcareers.service.gov.uk/discover-your-skills-and-careers/>

The 5 career counseling sessions were carried out through **in-depth interviews**. The research team adopted a developmental orientation approach, which is featured by **1)** raising the notion that a professional career is a process and **2)** use of descriptive and explanatory language to address the process of career development. From this approach, the process of career counseling is understood as “attempting to form an accurate and comprehensive picture of the client’s career development and encouraging the client to ‘move on’ in his or her development towards greater awareness of self and situation and competence in decision-making”.¹⁰

The interview questions were conducted following an adaptation of the FIRST framework: Focus, Information, Realism, Scope, and Tactics. Establishing the purpose of the interview, trying to create a friendly environment, providing information, and identifying some of the interviewee’s needs were some of the techniques applied by the research team.

All this research process allowed the ARDD Program Department to select the final participants and match them with a suitable TVET program and institution. ARDD mapped out over 50 public and private TVET and skills providers. From this figure, ARDD pre-selected 16 TVET and skills providers and 8 of them were contacted by email and phone calls.¹¹ The selection of the TVET provider was based on the following criteria: **1)** Availability of the TVET and skills programs the beneficiaries were interested in and/or capacity to tailor them to the beneficiaries’ needs and interests; **2)** acceptability and previous experience with refugees, **3)** registration and enrollment requirements, and **4)** affordability. Against these criteria, 3 TVET providers were short-listed: KUTC, Luminus Technical University College, and Best Supporters. Eventually, KUTC was selected as the TVET/Skills center for the ARDD-VHI scholarship program because it was the only institution from the selected ones that provided official accreditation to the students upon completion of the course, delivered TVET in all work fields which the youth was interested in (ensuring equal access to educational opportunities), offered flexibility in terms of registration/enrollment documentation, had a large experience training refugees from all nationalities (including Yemenis, Somalis, and Sudanese), and their financial proposal met ARDD-VHI budget.

Once the 15 beneficiaries were selected, confirmed, and started their TVET/Skills training, ARDD monitored the learning journey at KUTC. The monitoring process was based on baseline and end-line surveys, addressing 4 dimensions: personal, legal, social, and environmental. A WhatsApp Chat Group with the participants was set up for monitoring purposes as well. This individual monitoring process throughout the TVET/Skills scholarship aimed to have a comprehensive and holistic vision of their learning journey ultimately to better understand the key factors for students’ success. Beneficiaries who **dropped out** once (pre-) selected or during the TVET experience have also been documented.

Regarding the analysis of the TVET system in Jordan and TVET and skills for refugees, ARDD conducted **13 key informant interviews (KIIs)** with public and private TVET institutions (Business Development Center, Collateral Repair Project, Amala, Sawiyan, Jesuit Refugee Service, Vocational Training Company (VTC)), government bodies (Technical and Vocational Skills Development Commission (TVSDC)), donors (Agence Française de Développement, European Union (EU), Gemeinschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ), Global Affairs Canada (GAC), Swiss Embassy in Jordan, and UN agencies (UNHCR).

Furthermore, on June 13th, 2023 and 29th April, 2024, ARDD hosted two roundtables, one per each date, to discuss, respectively, the preliminary and final findings of this research. These events reunited stakeholders from different sectors (UN agencies, private sector, public and private TVET providers, donors, governmental bodies, etc.) working in the field of TVET and skills education in Jordan. The feedback provided by such stakeholders has also been included in this research.

10 Kidd, J. M. «The Career Counselling Interview.» In *Rethinking Careers Education and Guidance: Theory, Policy and Practice*, edited by A. G. Watts, B. Law, J. Killeen, J. M. Kidd, and R. Hawthorn (London: Routledge, 1996.), 194-195.

11 1) KUTC, 2) Luminus Technical University College, 3) Theodor Schneller School, 4) Bait Paris Academy, 5) Wasel for Awareness & Education, 6) SAE Institute Jordan - Creative Media Education, 7) Laval Academy, 8) Best Supporters.

Limitations

Certain limitations need to be considered.

Firstly, the **stability of the analysis pool**, i.e., the beneficiaries. One of the objectives of this research was to monitor the journey of 15 students since they were selected until they finished their TVET/Skills training. Nevertheless, the group of 15 initially selected students was not the same as the one who finalized the TVET/Skills program. Drop-outs were documented at different stages of the research process, but mainly they took place immediately before signing the contract accepting the TVET/Skills scholarship.

Secondly, the **lack of disaggregated data by non-Syrian nationalities from UNHCR sources:**

- **UNHCR Vocational Training mapping tool:** UNHCR conducted a mapping of TVET providers operating across Jordan. The data are disaggregated by a set of different variables, including nationality. Nevertheless, the tool only differentiates between Jordanians, Syrian and non-Syrian refugees, without providing clear disaggregated data within this latter category.
- **2022 UNHCR Vulnerability Assessment Framework (VAF) for Refugees Living in Host Communities:** ARDD welcomes UNHCR efforts to include non-Syrian refugees' data in its yearly vulnerability assessment for refugees living in host communities. However, still, many data are not disaggregated by nationality, falling into the general category of "non-Syrian refugees".

The disaggregation of the data by nationality (beyond the tag of "non-Syrian refugee" or "refugees from other nationalities") by UNHCR and other sources would enrich and ease the conduct of this research.

Lastly, we encountered some challenges in engaging certain stakeholders, particularly donors, during this research. Although ARDD successfully interviewed a representative sample of donors supporting TVET programming in Jordan, there were some who, despite our efforts, did not respond to our inquiries. We hope this situation will be rectified in future research.

SECTION I:

Yemeni, Somali, and Sudanese asylum seekers and refugees in Jordan

I.1 Overview of key areas of vulnerabilities

Yemeni, Somali, and Sudanese AS/R in Jordan face several inter-connected vulnerabilities. In order to provide an overview of such vulnerabilities, ARDD has delved into the following three key dimensions: **1) Legal status and documentation**, **2) Livelihoods, income, and indebtedness**, and **3) Education**. This literature review has used as a main source the comprehensive and critical *Vulnerability Assessment Framework: Population survey of refugees living in host communities - Jordan 2022* (2022 VAF hereinafter) conducted yearly by UNHCR.

I.1.1 Legal status and documentation

From an international legal standpoint, it's important to note that **Jordan has not ratified the 1951 UN Convention Relating to the Status of Refugees or its 1967 Protocol**, and therefore, it is not legally bound by the obligations outlined in these treaties. However, Article 21 (i) of the Jordanian Constitution prohibits the extradition of political refugees¹². Additionally, all states, including Jordan, are obligated by the international customary law principle of *non-refoulement*, which prohibits the forced expulsion or return of refugees to a country where their lives or freedom would be at risk.

Furthermore, Jordan does not have a formal domestic refugee or asylum law or policy. Instead, the UNHCR is responsible for determining refugee status under the 1998 Memorandum of Understanding between the UN refugee agency and the Jordanian government.

However, it's important to highlight that in January 2019, the Jordanian government decided to suspend UNHCR from registering non-Syrian asylum seekers and refugees (AS/R), effectively discriminating against them based on their nationality. This registration ban has created a legal gap between non-Syrian AS/R who arrived in Jordan before and after January 2019, denying the latter the ability to apply for asylum, obtain legal status, or access related benefits such as resettlement or humanitarian assistance.

This ban has particularly affected Yemeni AS/R, perpetuating existing disparities between registered and non-registered individuals. In 2015, the Jordanian Department of Statistics estimated that approximately 31,000 Yemenis were living in Jordan, a significant number compared to those registered with UNHCR. Many Yemenis had obtained residency permits through various means such as student visas, employment, or informal arrangements, without formalizing their status.¹³

The limited rights related to the “diminished” legal status of these communities directly impacts their socioeconomic circumstances, including their ability to work freely. Non-Syrian AS/R in Jordan face several challenges in this regard:

a) Work permit:

Under Jordanian labor law, non-Jordanian workers are required to obtain a work permit from the Ministry of Labor (MoL) in order to legally work in Jordan. Fines and other penalties may be imposed on both employers and foreign workers if they do not follow the legal procedures.¹⁴ Among these penalties, as the human rights organization Human Rights Watch reported, the Jordanian authorities have applied arrest, imprisonment, and **deportation** which **breach the principle of non-refoulement**, the backbone of international refugee law.¹⁵ Despite the accusations, the GoJ claims that it “*does effectively apply the principle of non-refoulement in its dealings with refugees on national soil*”.¹⁶

¹² Art. 21 (i) 1952 Constitution of the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan.

¹³ Solenn Al-Majali, *A Precarious Refuge: Yemeni Asylum-Seekers in Jordan* (February 2022), <https://sanaacenter.org/publications/main-publications/16557>.

¹⁴ UNHCR, *Working in Jordan*, <https://help.unhcr.org/jordan/en/helpful-services-unhcr/working-in-jordan/>

¹⁵ Human Rights Watch, *Jordan: Yemeni Asylum Seekers Deported* (March 2021), <https://www.hrw.org/news/2021/03/30/jordan-yemeni-asylum-seekers-deported>

¹⁶ A/HRC/40/10/Add.1.

Affordability is the principal problem for getting a work permit. According to the MoL, issuing or renewing work permits, including extra sums, range from JOD 150 to 2,220,¹⁷ depending on the sector, worker's skills, and duration.¹⁸ Pursuant to the law, the burden of paying the working permit fees is on the **employer**. Nonetheless, in practice, although the positive trend is to reduce the financial cost, employers are reluctant to assume it, forcing the AS/R to pay a share or the whole charge if they want to work. Unlike Syrian refugees, Yemeni, Somali, and Sudanese workers were not included in the 2016 Jordan Compact. Thus, they do not enjoy a waiver from the work permit fees, making their access to the labor market even more difficult.¹⁹ Despite the international and local NGOs' advocacy efforts for extending this waiver to non-Syrian refugees, work permit fees are placed as the major barrier for these communities in Jordan. The **excessive bureaucracy** and the **long duration of the work permit application procedure** have been identified as another challenge by foreign workers, including refugees.

b) Closed professional sectors:

AS/R in Jordan, due to their foreign status, cannot work in all professional sectors, but only in those expressly open to non-Jordanians by the MoL.²⁰ In this list, there are very low-skilled jobs, such as plastic factory worker or car washer, but also high technical profiles - computer network expert or aircraft security officer

c) Refugee legal status vs. formal worker:

Since 2020, non-Syrian AS/R in Jordan "need (...) to choose whether to maintain their international protection application or to apply for a work permit".²¹ A study conducted by Dr. Rochelle Johnston *et al.* stated that "government officials have told Yemeni asylum seekers and refugees that they need to de-register with UNHCR if they want to apply for a work permit"²² and "a couple of Sudanese refugees have been detained because they applied for work permits".²³ In other words, although there is no official policy or legislation issued by the Ministry of Interior (MoI) or MoL, allegedly holding the refugee legal status and working formally for non-Syrian AS/R are mutually exclusive.

d) Mobility restrictions:

Generally, registered Yemeni, Somali, and Sudanese AS/R enjoy freedom of domestic movement across the country. Nevertheless, those non-registered within UNHCR or without all the required legal documentation may not leave their place of residence, as they can be stopped by Jordanian authorities and face severe legal consequences, including deportation. This reduces their livelihood opportunities as they must work in or close to their hometown.

Documentation is another legal concern for Yemeni, Somali and Sudanese AS/R in Jordan. As research by ARDD²⁴ points out, in forced displacement contexts, a large number of displaced persons do not have the correct legal and civil documentation, preventing them from enjoying freedom of movement and access to education, health, and any other public service.

The initial challenge concerning documentation stems from the government restriction imposed in January 2019. Yemenis, Somalis, and Sudanese who arrived in the Kingdom after this date have been barred from registering as refugees with UNHCR, thus rendering them ineligible to obtain and benefit from the UNHCR card.

Secondly, another documentation issue is related to their **entry**. Unlike Syrian refugees, who crossed the land borders, most of these AS/R arrived in Jordan by air, meaning they held a valid passport at that time. Generally, Yemenis and Sudanese came to Jordan on a medical visa. Also, many Sudanese migrated to Jordan to work and decided to stay before the escalation of the conflict in their homeland.²⁵ Nevertheless, there are recorded instances in which some Sudanese and Somalis entered with forged documents.²⁶

17 For instance, a work permit issued for 6 months for a worker with specialized skills costs JD 2,200, meanwhile, a general one-year work permit is JD 400.

18 Adaleh Center for Legal Information, *An amended system for work permit fees for non-Jordanians No. 3 of 2022*, Official Gazette No. 5765 (February 2022), <http://www.adaleh.info/Art.aspx?Typ=2&Id=1356>

19 In April 2016, the Government of Jordan declared that Syrian refugees were exempted from paying fees related to work permit issuance or renewal or stamps until the end of that year. Jordanian authorities have renewed the waiver until the end of 2023. See MoL, *Employment of Syrian refugees*, https://www.mol.gov.jo/AR/Pages/%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%B9%D9%85%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%A9_%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%B3%D9%88%D8%B1%D9%8A%D8%A9

20 https://www.mol.gov.jo/EBV4.0/Root_Storage/AR/EB_Info_Page/%D9%85%D9%84%D8%A7%D8%AD%D9%82_%D8%A7%D9%84%D9%88%D8%AB%D9%8A%D9%82%D8%A9_%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%AA%D8%AC%D9%85%D9%8A%D8%B9%D9%8A%D8%A9.pdf

21 UNHCR, *Vulnerability Assessment Framework: Population survey of refugees living in host communities - Jordan 2022* (20 June 2022), 152, <https://data.unhcr.org/en/documents/details/93754>

22 Dr. Rochelle Johnston, Dina Baslan and Anna Kvittinge, *Realizing the rights of asylum seekers and refugees in Jordan from countries other than Syria with a focus on Yemenis and Sudanese* (April 2019), 23.

23 *Idem*.

24 ARDD, *Documentation for Syrian Refugees in Jordan: Good practices and Challenges*, 2020, <https://ardd-jo.org/publication/documentation-for-syrian-refugees-in-jordan-good-practices-and-challenges-working-paper/>

25 Dr. Rochelle Johnston *et al. idem.*, 6 – 9.

26 Mixed Migration Center, *Displaced Minorities Part I: Migration and displacement trends of Somali, Sudanese and Yemeni refugees and*

Lastly, there is a noticeable lack of updated documentation and access to corresponding civil and legal procedures due to the reluctance or inability of these communities to utilize their national consular services. Sudanese AS/R face an unwillingness issue, as the Sudanese Embassy collaborated with Jordanian authorities to deport Sudanese AS/R in 2015²⁷, and there are reported cases of harassment by embassy staff against them²⁸. As for Somalis, the situation differs significantly. With no Somali Embassy in Jordan, they are officially required to address their consulate needs to the Embassy of Somalia in Riyadh. However, in practice, members of the Somali community often rely on relatives, friends, acquaintances, or unofficial focal points to handle matters directly in Somalia or the Somali Embassies in Egypt or Saudi Arabia. Conversely, Yemenis have a better relationship with their diplomatic mission in Amman.

I.1.2 Livelihoods, income & indebtedness

The absence of access to the work permit system has compelled Yemeni, Somali, and Sudanese AS/R to seek employment in the informal sector. According to the 2022 VAF, in 2021, only **29% of non-Syrian refugees were employed**: Yemenis have better scores with a 46%, followed by Sudanese (30%) and Somalis (18%).²⁹ COVID 19 pandemic hardly hit the Jordanian economy and in terms of access to work among these communities, Somali refugees have been the most affected ones: 23% reported to have lost their jobs because of the Corona crisis.³⁰ On the contrary, Sudanese are those with the highest unemployment rate (16%).³¹

This data should be framed in a wider context where the **labor participation of non-Syrian refugees is 43%**.³² Note that having a disability impairment is ranked as the second most common reason for non-Syrians for being out of the labor force or not working.³³

For those who are currently working, however, **conditions are very poor**: carrying heavy loads, being exposed constantly to risks (extreme cold or heat, dust and fumes, loud noise or vibrations...), long working hours, being paid partially or not being paid, no days off, working without contracts, etc. are some of the daily abuses they are exposed to.³⁴ Also, AS/R have claimed to feel humiliated at their workplace by their employers.

Concerning the professional sectors they work in, according to the information provided by the organizations interviewed and the FGDs, Sudanese men tend to work in the wholesale food market, particularly, in the Sahab vegetable and fruit market (Amman), while women do so in the beauty and cosmetics sector (as they master the henna drawing art). Yemenis are more prone to work in restaurants and the food processing industry, and Somalis often work in cleaning jobs and others.

Regarding income, the report of the UN Agency estimates that the **average total monthly income of a non-Syrian family is JOD 202**: JOD 223 for Yemenis, JOD 191 for the Sudanese, and JOD 273 when it comes to Somali AS/R. The sources of income vary depending on the nationality: while for Sudanese and Yemeni refugee households work is the main one, Somali refugees obtain the bulk of their income from UNHCR and World Food Program assistance. Remittances and sporadic cash assistance from NGOs constitute, although in a lower amount, another source of economic support for them to rely on.³⁵

The income shortcoming has obliged these households to get into debt to afford basic needs. **Debt per capita on average for non-Syrians refugees stands at 792,3 JOD**: by nationality, Yemenis, even though their employment rates and incomes are comparatively quite high, are the ones who report the highest average debt per capita (900.4 JOD).³⁶

other migrants in Jordan (April 2017), 6, https://reliefweb.int/report/jordan/displaced-minorities-part-i-migration-and-displacement-trends-somali-sudanese-and?gclid=CjwKCAjw8symBhAqEiwAaTA__LxXzOI2FZSUNo_JcX7XPUY6bXzkbpFBgAN-IC0jcLGty2RC-m3Qv-BoC-BgQAvD_BwE

²⁷ Note that the majority of Sudanese AS/R in Jordan are originally from conflicted-affected areas (Darfur, Nuba Mountains and East Sudan) which has traditionally opposed Omar Al Bashir and successive Governments, being the reason why government official may take retaliatory measures against them.

²⁸ Dr. Rochelle Johnston *et al idem.*, 50.

²⁹ UNCHR, *ibid.*, 153, 155.

³⁰ *Idem.*

³¹ UNHCR, *ibid.*, 167.

³² UNCHR, *ibid.*, 153.

³³ UNHCR, *ibid.*, 169.

³⁴ UNHCR, *ibid.*, 160, 161.

³⁵ UNHCR, *ibid.*, 163.

³⁶ UNHCR, *ibid.*, 146.

I.1.3 Education

Despite education being acknowledged as a fundamental human right, Yemenis, Somalis, and Sudanese continue to encounter numerous obstacles in accessing education. Among these, the primary issue concerns limited access. Former Minister of Education and Higher Education and Scientific Research (MoE), his excellency Prof. Mohammad Thneibat, claimed “we have opened our school doors to Syrian children as well as all other (children) living on the soil of Jordan regardless of their nationality or reasons why they are in Jordan”.³⁷ However, Somali, Sudanese and Yemeni children and teenagers struggle to enroll in government primary and secondary schools in Jordan.

Policies governing this topic have changed over time. As a general rule, foreigners must possess annual residency in Jordan and not be out of school for three or more years in order to register in primary and secondary schools. This requirement applies to non-Syrian AS/R. At the beginning of 2018, NGOs started reporting these communities were requested to provide proof of residence to succeed in the enrollment process. The situation was confirmed by Prime Minister Omar Razzaz’s Letter explicitly waiving only Syrian refugees of documentation requirements. Nonetheless, using its discretion power, the MoE and the majority of schools allowed non-Syrian AS/R to register only with their UNHCR Asylum Seeker Certificate. The scenario radically changed in June 2020, when MoI ordered MoE and Jordanian schools to only register non-Jordanians with residency (*Iqama*) or work permits. After a joint advocacy effort, in 2022, MoE waived such documentation requirements on the condition of correcting their legal status and the situation in Jordan.³⁸

In addition, there are several cases where, after going through this unclear and complex process, these AS/R communities face negative enrollment answers from schools as they are full of students. Jordanian citizens should have priority, some of the schools argue.³⁹

The difficulties above mentioned, together with other factors, impact the school enrollment figures: 17% of Yemeni, Sudanese, and Somali school-aged children have never attended school.⁴⁰

Socioeconomic barriers have been identified as relevant impairments for the full realization of Sudanese, Somali, and Yemeni AS/R’s educational rights.

From an economic perspective, unlike Syrian refugees, these communities, as non-Jordanians, have to pay a **JOD 40 annual fee for public school enrollment**, besides the books, school materials and transportation costs. These expenses can be prohibitive for families with very low incomes, as UNHCR indicates in the 2022 VAF pointing out that **financial constraints** are one of the main reasons to drop out. In many cases, families restore to private donors to pay them, or the education services are directly provided outside the state system by volunteer teachers from the community.

Lack of devices and weak or not Internet connection also rank high among the challenges faced.⁴¹ For instance, a study conducted by the Jesuit Refugee Service (JRS) shows that 62% of the non-Syrian AS/R surveyed reported that their school-aged children could not enroll on the MoE online platform daily.⁴² The lack of technical and economic resources only reinforces “the stereotype of poor helpless refugees.”⁴³

Finally, **bullying** is another deterrent element to be taken into account in analyzing diminished access to education of these communities. The school harassment by their classmates ranges from verbal abuse to physical violence, including social isolation. Sudanese and Somali AS/R especially suffer bullying mainly based on their skin color. This social scourge not only comes from some Jordanian students but also teachers: if Somali, Sudanese, or Yemeni students perform better than their peers, they are not encouraged to continue on that path; some of them deliberately neglect the bullying episodes and have confronted the parents of these students.⁴⁴

37 UNICEF, *Jordan Commits to provide Education to Every Child* (22 August 2016), <https://reliefweb.int/report/jordan/jordan-commits-provide-education-every-child>

38 One Refugee Approach Working Group & Advocacy Committee, *Education Barriers in Jordan for Non-Syrian Refugees*, <https://data.unhcr.org/en/documents/download/86982>

39 Dr. Rochelle Johnston *et al* *ibid.*, 32.

40 UNHCR, *ibid.*, 126.

41 UNHCR, *ibid.*, 132.

42 One Refugee Approach Working Group & Advocacy Committee *idem.*, 7.

43 Mixed Migration Center, *ibid.*, 5.

44 Dr. Rochelle Johnston *et al* *ibid.*, 33, 34.

SECTION II:

Technical and vocational education and training in Jordan

II.1 Overview of TVET and skills

Jordanian general education starts at age 5 and runs to age 15 (primary and lower secondary). After completion of grade 10, pupils leaving primary school are streamed into academic or vocational tracks based on their scores. The highest-scoring students often continue to upper secondary education, while the remaining students enter vocational education programs (or vocational training if their score is below 50%). Upper secondary ends with the *Tawjihi* – the national secondary certificate exam. Only students who pass the *Tawjihi* are eligible to move on to higher education.⁴⁵

Upper secondary TVET enrollment in Jordan is very low and rarely leads to higher education opportunities.

Students who entered the vocational education path, can continue to upper secondary TVET. However, in 2017, only 14% of upper secondary students were enrolled in vocational programs and 10% of university students were enrolled in TVET-oriented community colleges.

One of the factors contributing to this low enrollment is that students in VTC programs often fail to pass the *Tawjihi* exams and consequently have limited options for further education. While community colleges accept students with general secondary education certificates, regardless of their *Tawjihi* results, those who do pass the *Tawjihi* can pursue technical-level courses leading to national comprehensive exams (Al Shamel). However, despite this pathway, only a small fraction, approximately 5%, of community college graduates proceed to universities.

Formal TVET is delivered in three main subsystems:⁴⁶

- 1 VTC:** It is a semi-autonomous governmental institution, governed by a board of directors headed by the Minister of Labour. Under the VTC Law No. (11) of 1985, the VTC provides different types of technical and vocational training programs: basic skills level programs, technical upgrading programs, short courses and local society services, and occupational safety and health training programs. Trainings in the VTC are provided in different modalities: institutional training, on-the-job training, and dual system.⁴⁷ VTC has 35 operating vocational training center, having an operational capacity of 10 to 20 thousand trainees per year.⁴⁸
 - Similar TVET programs are also provided by the National Employment and Training Company (NET) and the United Nations Relief and Works Agency.
- 2 Ministry of Education:** It provides vocational education programs which last 2 years at the secondary education level, covering different specializations in four economic sectors (industrial, agriculture, hotel and tourism, and home economics). They reach more than 29,000 students in 214 locations.⁴⁹
- 3 Community colleges:** Under the Al-Balqa' Applied University (BAU) direct authority/supervision, the 51 community colleges offer the following TVET:
 - Technical education programs for students with *Tawjihi* that last 2 to 3 years.
 - Vocational training programs for students who have completed secondary education (with or without the *Tawjihi*) that last 1 or 2 years.⁵⁰

While the TVET system in Jordan is dominated by public providers, there are over 50 private / non-governmental educational entities providing skills and vocational education courses. (See section III.1 Availability of TVET and skills training)

⁴⁵ ETF, *National qualifications framework – Jordan* (2021), 5.

⁴⁶ Other formal TVET systems/providers are private sector vocational education, Al-Hussein Technical University – Crowne Prince Foundation, and vocational training affiliated to line Ministries.

⁴⁷ https://vtc.gov.jo/En/Pages/About_Us

⁴⁸ TVSDC, *National TVET Strategy 2023 – 2027*, 33.

⁴⁹ *Ibid.* 31.

⁵⁰ Similar TVET programs are also offered by the Jordanian Armed Forces.

II.2 Current TVET and skills strategy

There are two strategies formulating the future of TVET and Skills education in Jordan, namely:

1 National TVET Strategy 2023 – 2027: Also known as Jordan TVET Reform Plan or Triple 888 plan, its main objective is to reform the TVET sector in Jordan in 5 years, is “to promote skills acquisition, enhance governance, quality, and relevance of the TVET systems to equip all youth and adults with the skills required for employment, decent work, entrepreneurship, and lifelong learning”.⁵¹ In order to achieve this goal, this strategy is structured in three main pillars:

- Pillar I: Improving governance of the TVET sector and institutional development.
- Pillar II: Enhancing the quality and the relevance of TVET to meet the Jordanian labor market needs.
- Pillar III: Ensure the attractiveness of TVET for students and job seekers, and the employability of TVET graduates in their specializations.

1 Vocational Education Reform Strategic Plan 2022-2027.⁵²

II.3 Challenges of the Jordanian TVET system

Based on the available literature on TVET and skills in Jordan and the information provided in the KIIs, the development and strengthening of the current national TVET and skills system is hampered by the following institutional, legal, and economic barriers and gaps:

a) Unimplemented governance framework

The current TVET governance system is characterized by its fragmentation and lack of coordination among the stakeholders involved. MoE, MoL, BAU, VTC, NET, and TVSDC are all competent (to different extents) in TVET delivery and regulation. The high number of stakeholders combined with an unclear delimitation of their competencies have led to overlaps and gaps, lack of accountability and miscoordination.

The creation of the TVSDC in 2019 attempted to put an end to the pre-existing weak governance structure of TVET in Jordan. Nevertheless, it has been unable to serve as the institutional and regulatory focal point of TVET and coordinate with other relevant stakeholders, despite having the competencies to do so.

Additionally, it should be raised that the whole current TVET governance structure could be affected by the reform of the MoE, whose approval is pending on a final decision of the Prime Ministry. The MoE may become the Ministry of Education and Human Resources Development and may take over the TVET file.⁵³

b) Insufficient coordination among donors

Although the support of the international aid community is pivotal for the consolidation of the Jordanian TVET system, it should be done in a strategic and coordinated manner, avoiding overlaps, and identifying linkages and synergies.

Under the EU-funded project “Technical Assistance to the Skills for Employment and Social Inclusion Program”, GIZ developed “A donor coordination strategy for the TVET sector in Jordan”⁵⁴ to be adopted for the period 2019-2025. No reference to this strategy was made in any of the interviews conducted with donors.

Another conclusion all donors interviewed agreed on is that there is no centralized coordination mechanism for donors in TVET. The Education Sector Working Group, the Education Development Partners Group, and the ILO Skills Development Working Group were the most cited institutional venues for donor coordination in TVET during the interview process.

c) Limited funding and inefficient financial strategies

The Jordanian education budget is limited in terms of providing sufficient funds for the development and expansion of TVET and skills programs. In 2016, GoJ expended on TVET only 3,6% of the total education budget.⁵⁵ To expand the funding base, a training fund called the “E-TVET Fund” (now TVET Support Fund) was established to support TVET activities and the public and private cooperation. Such a Fund relies on funding collected from foreign workers’ work permit fees. In 2023, the TVSDC TVET Support Fund budget was JD 12,7. Although it is a significant increase from previous years (JD 3,6 in 2022), still is not enough to cope with the employment and training needs.⁵⁶

51 TVSDC, *Ibid.*, 38.

52 ARDD has had no access to the cited policy document.

53 KII.

54 <https://tvsvc.gov.jo/wp-content/uploads/2020/11/TVET-donor-coordination-strategy-ENG.docx>

55 UNESCO – UNEVOC, “TVET Country Profile: Jordan” (Amman, 2019), p. 5, <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000373090>

56 TVSDC *ibid.*, 37, 38.

However, the limited number of financial resources allocated to TVET is not the main concern, but the public financial management system applied. Funds are allocated to public TVET and skills providers based on the previous year's funding levels and trends, regardless of the outcomes and performance. So, unlike the private TVET and skills providers, there is no outcomes or performance-based financial management system in place. This clearly disincentives public TVET and skills providers to improve the quality and outcomes of their vocational and technical programs, as they know the GoJ will allocate a similar amount of funds.⁵⁷

d) TVET programs and curricula

TVET and skills programs are generally not demand-driven, but supply-driven. There is a clear mismatch between the TVET and skills supply and the Jordanian labor market needs. Public and private TVET and skills providers should provide relevant TVET and skills opportunities according to the previously assessed labor market needs. Therefore, further skills intelligence studies on TVET in Jordan should be conducted.

Despite the above mentioned, the following nuance should be made: vocational training provided by private TVET institutions are more demand-oriented than public ones. The rationale is different between NGOs and non-NGO TVET and skills providers.

With respect to NGOs, they have the mandate and willingness to support vulnerable communities, both refugees and host population, to improve their education and livelihoods. Therefore, they assess the needs of such communities in order to provide them with a comprehensive and holistic response. All interviewed NGOs providing TVET and skills to Yemeni, Somali, and Sudanese AS/R agreed that all their vocational and technical training programs were delivered in accordance with a previously identified need and requested by the beneficiaries. Unfortunately, due to a lack of capacity and underfunding, some local NGOs cannot provide TVET programs that are 100% tailored to the beneficiaries' needs and expectations.

On the other hand, non-NGO TVET institutions, as they are mainly profit-driven, modify and update their programs, taking into account statistics (drop-outs, attendance, qualifications...) and participants' feedback.

Regarding **TVET and skills curricula**, as key informants and students have pointed out, they tend to focus on **technical knowledge, neglecting the soft skills component** (e.g., English, entrepreneurship, digital literacy, financial literacy, etc.). Soft skills should be considered as important as technical skills during the TVET curricula design process. Furthermore, gender and ability should be mainstreamed in TVET curricula.

e) Weak or no engagement with the private sector

TVET programs and their curricula are designed with weak or no participation from the private sector. Hence, it is necessary to strengthen the public-private partnership in this regard. The private sector should play a key role in making TVET more labor-oriented, transitioning from a TVET supply-driven model toward a demand-driven one. For instance, co-designing TVET curricula with the private sector will correct the mismatch between the skills learned by the students and the skills needed by the labor market. Organizing national events gathering the private sector, TVET institutions, and trainees has demonstrated to be very effective when it comes to gaining the private sector's trust in TVET students.⁵⁸

f) TVET facilities and equipment

TVET facilities and equipment are old-fashioned and insufficient, particularly the public ones, not training the students for the reality of work. By not incorporating the latest scientific and technological developments, Jordan is missing an excellent opportunity for forging a more competitive and modern workforce able to meet the market demands.⁵⁹

g) TVET trainers and teachers

Jordan has a concerning shortcoming in qualified technical and vocational trainers, particularly in the public sector.⁶⁰ Generally, teachers and trainers lack practical experience and pedagogical skills. In order to overcome this problem, VTC has been recruiting trainers with extensive work experience, but without success, as they are unable to transfer this practical knowledge to the trainees because they do not have the necessary teaching skills.⁶¹ Hence, further and regular training for teachers in public TVET institutions, paying particular attention to pedagogical skills, is needed.

⁵⁷ EFT *ibid.*, 8.

⁵⁸ KII.

⁵⁹ VTC, Strategic Plan (2020-2022), https://vtc.gov.jo/ebv4.0/root_storage/en/eb_list_page/strategic_plan_2020.pdf

⁶⁰ Higher Population Council, *Empowering the Employment, Vocational and Technical Education and Training Sector* (2015), https://www.hpc.org.jo/sites/default/files/Technical%20education%20training-Policy%20brief_0.pdf

⁶¹ EFT, *Quality assurance in vocational education and training in Jordan. ETF Forum Member Institution: TVSDC* (April 2020), 10 https://www.etf.europa.eu/sites/default/files/2021-01/quality_assurance_in_vet_jordan.pdf

h) Inclusion

In terms of gender and inclusion, TVET is still a stream heavily dominated by men, particularly, those fields regarding science, technology, engineering, and mathematics. TVET-related professions are culturally more acceptable to men than to women. Nevertheless, the involvement of women's in technical and vocational training has gradually increased over the past years. Timetabling is one of the main issues pointed out by key informants hindering women's participation in TVET, as they have to reconcile it with their caregiver duties.

On the other hand, when it comes to ability and inclusion, it should be highlighted that persons with disabilities' participation in TVET is particularly limited. Adopting and implementing enabling regulations; adapting the materials, infrastructure, and evaluation systems according to their special needs, and tackling the social stigma towards persons with disabilities are some of the actions that need to be taken to move forward to a more inclusive TVET system in Jordan.⁶²

Linked to the previous challenges, in order to make TVET more inclusive, it is crucial to train TVET teachers and trainers in inclusion and diversity in education.

Lastly, although huge efforts have been done to increase the participation of Syrian refugees into TVET, still it is an educational pathway not fully accessible for all refugees (See Sections II.5 and III.1).

i) Poor social image of TVET

As in many other countries, there is a widespread perception among Jordanians that TVET is a less desirable option compared to traditional academic pathways. The low cultural perception of TVET is mainly due to "poor quality, weak linkages with stakeholders particularly the industries, social stigma, cultural barriers, and a lack of qualified and competent teachers".⁶³ In addition, Jordanian society perceives that vocational and technical professions are associated with a lack of social protection coverage (i.e., social security, health insurance and decent working conditions). For these reasons, young people are discouraged by their families and friends to enroll in a TVET program. TVET is seen as an option only in case of failure in the academic stream.

j) Limited transition pathways in the Jordanian educational system

The Jordanian educational system does not generally allow students to move from the vocational and technical stream to the academic one and vice versa.

k) Limited investment by private and public TVET and skills providers in career guidance and counseling.

II.4 Initiatives to enhance TVET system in Jordan

Among the initiatives seeking to enhance TVET education in Jordan:

a) Jordanian National Qualifications Framework (JNQF)

Adopted via a bylaw in January 2019, the JNQF is a 10-level, learning outcomes-based, comprehensive framework covering qualifications from general education to higher education, including TVET. It aims to facilitate permeability among the different education and training sectors of the Jordanian system, enhance TVET quality and make the technical and vocational stream more attractive to students. In cooperation with TVSDC, its implementation is under the responsibility of the Accreditation and Quality Assurance Commission for Higher Education Institutions, which has already developed strategic and operational plans, policies, and standards for all levels of TVET.

b) Skills intelligence

This term refers to the ability to identify, measure and utilize technical and vocational skills within the context of education and training programs. Skills intelligence gathering and analysis to support human capital development and the response of vocational education and training systems to the labor market and societal needs.⁶⁴

Among the tools that enhance skills intelligence are **tracer studies**. These aim to assess the situation of the graduates of a particular education or training program, typically 6, 12, or 24 months after graduation. This type of study contributes to better understanding the school-to-work transition of recent graduates. For instance, UNESCO conducted a relevant tracer study in the hospitality and tourism sector in Jordan.⁶⁵

62 UNESCO & MoE, Jordan TVET System Review. Technical and Vocational Education and Training (Unpublished), 154.

63 TVSDC *ibid.*, 79.

64 <https://www.etf.europa.eu/en/what-we-do/skills-intelligence>

65 UNESCO, *Tracer Study of Tourism-and-Hospitality Vocational Secondary Education in Jordan* (2019), <https://jordan.un.org/sites/default/files/2021-09/English%20Tracer%20Study%20of%20Tourism-and-Hospitality%20Vocational%20Secondary%20Education%20in%20Jordan.pdf>

Other tools for skill intelligence are showcasing **local skills ecosystems**. The European Training Foundation (ETF) has been active over the years in promoting and showcasing local skills ecosystems in the countries where it works.

In 2015, Jordan provided a notable success story as part of the **ETF's Entrepreneurial Communities initiative**, aimed at showcasing examples of successful local partnerships for skills. The Jordanian entrepreneurial community was a partnership between two businesses - MENA Apps and Oasis500 - and Int@j, a private non-profit organization promoting the Jordanian software and IT services industry. The partnership combines incubation and acceleration services for tech start-ups with training, mentorship and coaching, networking services, and matchmaking with potential investors.⁶⁶

Another interesting initiative has been **Bena** (www.bena.org.jo) was established as an output of the project Training for Water and Energy Efficiency Development (TWEED). The TWEED project was implemented by GIZ on behalf of the German Federal Ministry of Economic Cooperation and Development and the Jordanian Ministry of Water and Irrigation. Bilateral agreements have been signed between GIZ, the Ministry of Water and Irrigation, and the implementing partner VTC. TWEED aimed to contribute through market-oriented vocational training to more efficient use of water and energy in the building sector.

The **Bena** website was intended as the main gateway that assists young people to experience the world of crafts. **Bena** informs young people about vocational training, job opportunities, and courses within the construction sector, especially in water and energy. It advises people interested in choosing a profession. The image of handi-craft occupations, especially blue-collar jobs, will be improved and awareness towards these occupations will be raised. The Jordanian Construction Contractors Association currently manages and operates the website.

c) Technical and Vocational Skills Development Commission

By recommendation of the National Strategy of Human Resources Development 2016 – 2025,⁶⁷ the TVSDC was established as the main regulatory body in TVET by Law (9) / 2019.

TVSDC works toward the attainment of the following goals: **1)** Being the focal point of governance of the TVET sector, **2)** Improving the quality of outputs of the TVET sector, **3)** Training the workforce to meet the needs of the Jordanian labor market, **4)** Enhancing the societal perception of TVET, and **5)** Contributing to the economic and social sustainable development.⁶⁸

In order to achieve these objectives, TVSDC is responsible for **a)** adopting the TVET sector's strategies, policies, and plans (including the National TVET Strategy 2023 - 2027), **b)** suggesting laws and regulations concerning TVET, **c)** approving occupational standards, **d)** accreditation and supervision of TVET providers, **e)** development of TVET programs standards, **f)** management of the TVET Support Fund, **g)** issuing of official certificates for informal workers, among others.⁶⁹

TVSDC is led by a TVSD Council. The Council is headed by the Minister of Labor, and it is composed of representatives from the MoE, the Ministry of Higher Education, the Secretary-General of the MoL, the Crown Prince Foundation, the private sector, the president of TVSDC (Dr. Raghda Al-Faouri), and the president of the Accreditation and Quality Assurance Commission for Higher Education.⁷⁰

It is important to stress that the TVSDC is currently working not only to foster decent and sustainable livelihood opportunities for Jordanians, but also, they are implementing projects targeting Syrian refugees (on-site training and certification), positively contributing to address the skills gaps and the high unemployment rates among youth in Jordan.

Another significant initiative undertaken by the TVSDC is the issuance of experience certificates to tackle the informality, supporting those workers working in the informal labor market to find new opportunities in the formal sector and increase their economic and social securities.

a) Donor support to strengthening the TVET sector in Jordan

ARDD has conducted a desk-review mapping of donors which are funding/have funded projects and programs aimed to strengthen and modernize the TVET system in Jordan. The timeframe for the TVET programs and projects mapped out is 2015 – 2025. The information was verified through interviews with key donor agency representatives, particularly from the EU, GIZ, and GAC.

66 "Local Skills in Jordan", <https://www.etf.europa.eu/en/news-and-events/news/local-skills-jordan>

67 Education for prosperity: Delivering results, A National Strategy for Human Resource Development 2016 – 2025, 31, <https://en.heac.org.jo/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/National-HRD-Strategy.pdf>

68 <https://tvsc.gov.jo/en/#tabs-8-3>

69 TVSDC, *ibid.*, 26,27.

70 *Ibid.*

The following table summarizes past and ongoing donors' efforts in Jordan to strengthen and modernize the national TVET system:

Table 1: Donor mapping of projects funded for strengthening the TVET sector in Jordan (2015 - 2025)

Donor	Project Name	Duration (2015 - 2025)
AICS	Education Sector budget support to the Government of Jordan	2019 - 2022
EU Delegation in Jordan / EU	Technical Assistance to Support the Quality of Education and TVET	2022 - 2024
	Technical Assistance to the Skills for Employment and Social Inclusion Programme	2017 - 2022
Foreign, Commonwealth and Development Office (FCDO)	Jordan Labour Market Programme	2017- 2021
BMZ/GIZ	Qualification oriented to employment in the craft	2017 - 2024
	Labour Market Oriented Vocational Education, Higher Education and Training (MOVE-HET) Phase I ⁷¹	2017 - 2023
Global Affairs Canada	Transforming Technical and Vocational Education in Jordan (Phase I) ⁷²	N/A - 2023
Japan International Cooperation Agency	Capacity Development of Vocational Training Corporation in the Field of Occupational Safety and Health	2017 - 2020
	Strengthening the Capacity for Career Counseling for the Youth	2017 -2020
Korean International Cooperation Agency	Establishment of Specialised Industrial School in Zarqa	2017 - 2020

II.5 TVET and skills for refugees in Jordan

Through the Jordan Compact agreed upon in 2016, the Jordanian government and the international community have sought to aid the Syrian refugees and their host communities by mobilizing significant funds in grants and loans. This money has enabled, among other projects, the provision of school enrollment and boosted labor market participation, of youth and women in particular.

Donors have identified technical and vocational trainings and skills programs as key tools to economically empower refugees, while positively contributing to the national economic growth of Jordan. In the timeframe of 2015-2025, ARDD has mapped out + 50 projects funded by 24 different donors (government development agencies, UN agencies, private entities, and public and/or private partnerships) whose goal was/is to provide TVET and skills opportunities to refugees, enhancing their technical and soft skills and increasing their employability and self-reliance. The desk-review information was verified through interviews with key donor agencies representatives, particularly, from the EU, GIZ, GAC, the Swiss Embassy in Jordan, and the Agence Française de Développement.

⁷¹ GIZ, EU, and GAC are currently moving forward to a second phase of the MOVE-HET.

⁷² GAC will fund a second phase of the project.

In terms of beneficiaries, for the past 10 years, TVET and skills projects for refugees in Jordan have targeted mainly youth and women (and persons with disabilities in some instances) with a strong Syrian focus, and only a few donors have funded interventions with a TVET and/or skills component including non-Syrian refugees, such as the Swiss Embassy in Jordan and GAC. This funding trend among donors undermines the One Refugee Approach and leaves out adults.

From the donor perspective, MoL policies allowing refugees only to work in specific professional sectors, impeding their full integration into the Jordanian labor market, is one of the principal barriers to further promoting TVET and skills among refugees, in particular, for non-Syrian refugees. The increase of the flexible work permit fees (from 77 to 155 JOD) and the contributions to social security (from 18 to 56,55 JOD),⁷³ the complex and time-consuming legal and administrative process to get the work permit, and the high fees of taking the TVET stream are other impediments for refugees willing to engage in TVET.

Taking into account these legal constraints, donors have funded projects aiming to foster different livelihood models: While some donors have been pushing for online jobs (particularly, for women and non-Syrian refugees), others have bet on formal in-person work or home-based business (mainly, for Syrian refugees).

TVET and skills interventions have been focused on specific economic sectors, purposefully coinciding with those professions open to non-Jordanians: agriculture, construction, manufacturing, garment, and hospitality.

Organized by donors, the following table sums up previous and current projects to create livelihood opportunities for refugees in Jordan through technical and vocational training and skills programs:

⁷³ Economic Empowerment Working Group Update October 2023.

Table 2: Simplified donor mapping of TVET and skills funded projects for fostering livelihood for refugees in Jordan (2015 - 2025) ⁷⁴

Donor classification	Donor
Governmental development aid agencies	Agence Française de développement
	Agenzia Italiana per la Cooperazione allo Sviluppo
	Australia Aid
	European Union Delegation in Jordan / EU
	FCDO
	German Development Bank (KfW)
	BMZ/GIZ
	Government of Finland
	Government of the Republic of Korea
	Japan International Cooperation Agency
	Norway Ministry of Foreign Affairs
	Dutch Ministry of Foreign Affairs
	USAID
	US Department of State’s Bureau of Population, Refugees, and Migration
Swedish International Development Cooperation Agency	
Swiss Agency for Development and Cooperation	
UN Agencies	UNICEF
	UNHCR
	WFP
Private donors	Yayasan Hasanah Foundation
	Novo Nordisk Foundation
Partnerships	Chloé, EU, KfW, Government of Netherlands
	EU, BMZ
	BMZ, Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Netherlands
	BMZ, Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Netherlands, FCDO
	Kuwait Foundation of the Advancement of Science, GAC
	EU, GIZ, AECID

⁷⁴ For further details, see Annex I.

SECTION III:

TVET and Skills for Yemeni, Somali and Sudanese ASR in Jordan

In order to analyze the inclusion of Yemeni, Somali, and Sudanese AS/R into the Jordanian TVET system, ARDD has adopted and adapted the **inclusion of refugees in TVET self-assessment tool** from the British Council to the Jordanian context.⁷⁵

This tool aims to “provide a practical and easy-to-navigate instrument for carrying out an analysis of the status of TVET in respect of refugees’ inclusion”.⁷⁶ It consists of 19 questions, with a score scale from 0 (minimum scoring) to 2 (maximum scoring), and analyses four dimensions: **1) Availability** of TVET opportunities for refugees, **2) Accessibility** of refugees to TVET programs, and **3) Acceptability** of TVET by refugees, and **4) Adaptability** of TVET to refugee needs.

ARDD customized this tool for research applications by focusing on the initial three analytical dimensions (availability, accessibility, and acceptability). Additionally, these dimensions were considered not only through an institutional lens, as originally intended but also from the perspective of students, offering a comprehensive understanding of TVET and skills development in Jordan.

III.1 Availability of TVET and skills training

This analytical dimension focused on the availability of TVET and skills opportunities to Yemeni, Somali, and Sudanese AS/R in Jordan. Availability was analyzed in terms of TVET and skills opportunities for these refugees (state and non-state-managed TVET institutions, TVET fields, TVET levels, etc.). ARDD mapped out over 50 TVET and skills providers in Jordan. The mapping was conducted through a desk-review process, looking at three main categories:

1) General TVET institution information, including

- Institution type (private / public & international / national).
- Eligible students (age range).
- Areas of service delivery.
- Delivery of the training (not) based on projects.

2) TVET and skills program: This category contains detailed information about the TVET program, which includes:

- Duration, which ranges between weeks and one year.
- Type of courses provided within two main fields:
 - **Soft skills courses**, such as computer literacy or life skills.
 - **Technical skills courses**, from blue-collar skills, such as automobile mechanics and swelling, to white-collar ones, for instance, accountant or web designer.
- Availability of career mentoring and counseling within the institution in general or within the program in particular.
- Program delivery method, divided into: On-site, hybrid and online program.
- Program fees and the availability of scholarships.
- Provision of certificate of completion at the end of the TVET/Skills training, including:

⁷⁵ British Council, *Inclusion of refugees in technical and vocational education and training. Self-assessment tool* (2019), https://www.british-council.org/sites/default/files/refugees_tvvet_self-assessment_toolkit_0.pdf

⁷⁶ *Idem*, p. 4.

- **Type of certification:** Official (those issued by centers which are homologated before the Ministry of Education and Higher Education) and self-issued by the center.
- **Certification recognition by other entities** inside or outside Jordan.

3) Key program registration requirement:

- Acceptance / previous experience with Syrian and non-Syrian AS/R. AS/R educational needs are particularly different than average Jordanian students due to their legal status. Therefore, the sensitivity of the TVET institution regarding AS/R's situation in Jordan was an essential element during the mapping process.
- Documentation (UNHCR card, ID card, application form, photography...).
- Previous educational qualifications. English level, Tawjihi and/or computer skills are the most common ones.

Table 3: Simplified mapping of TVET and skills providers in Jordan

TVET provider	General Information			TVET Program				Key registration information	
	International / Local	Public / Private	Project based	Duration	Types of courses offered		Registration requirements	Experience with refugees	Qualifications required
					Soft skills	Technical skills			
JRS	International	Private		Depending on the course (English B2, computer skills)					
NRC	International	Private		No specific requirements					
Amala	Local	Private		English Level B1, cover letter, <i>Tawjihi</i>					
VTC	Local	Public		Completion of 10th grade					
KUTC	Local	Private		No specific requirement					

III.2 Accessibility to TVET and skills training

This analytical dimension focused on the accessibility of TVET and skills opportunities to Yemeni, Somali and Sudanese AS/R in Jordan. Accessibility was analyzed in terms of legal documentation, the right to work and move freely (See Section I. 1.1.), and financial resources.

III.2.1 Legal barriers and documentation

The possession and presentation of valid identity documentation⁷⁷ is a requirement for enrollment in any vocational or technical training. As mentioned in the methodology section, of the 50 TVET and skills providers mapped, 9 were contacted and interviewed. When they were asked about the documentation they require from potential students, it has been identified a lack of uniform documentation policy. According to the TVET and skills providers consulted, two documentation patterns for refugees were found: **1) Valid ID and UNHCR card; and 2) valid ID, UNHCR card or residence permit.** Moreover, it should be highlighted that some non-formal or informal TVET centers, such as Amala, exceptionally may accept students without a valid ID card, basing their enrollment exclusively on their previous academic background. Other TVET and skills providers stated that they could accept outdated ID and/or UNHCR cards.

It is important to stress that in scenario **1)** there is a high risk of discrimination against asylum seekers. As it has been explained in section I.1.1., Jordanian authorities ordered UNHCR to refrain from registering non-Syrian refugees in January 2019, preventing them from having official refugee status. This means they cannot get a UNHCR card. Therefore, requesting a UNHCR card for a non-registered refugee to be able to enroll in technical or vocational training denies him/her access to it. A valid or outdated ID or UNHCR card or any other proof of identity should be enough for refugees and asylum seekers to access TVET and skills programs.

Depend on the TVET program and institution, TVET and skills providers may additionally ask for *Tawjihi* certificate, certified level of English, computer literacy, etc.

III.2.2 Fees and funding opportunities

Across the FGDs, participants, both Jordanians and non-Jordanians, identified **TVET and skills programs' fees** as the **primary obstacle to accessing** them. As per ARDD mapping, several TVET and skills institutions provide vocational and technical training opportunities freely in Amman for Jordanians and refugees alike, mainly INGOs and a few local organizations. From the account of the beneficiaries, two INGOs seem to be particularly committed to freely meeting the educational needs of Yemeni, Somali, and Sudanese AS/R in Jordan: the JRS and Collateral Repair Project (CRP). At the local level, Sawiyan was also highly mentioned. In this regard, from the beneficiary perspective, a key takeaway for NGOs, whether local or international, is the **improvement of the referral system** on TVET and skills providers, as many of the participants in the FGDs did not know how to find TVET and skills opportunities.

Despite the efforts of above-mentioned organizations, the private sector in Jordan has turned TVET and skills provision into a profitable venture, resulting in high costs that hinder both refugees and Jordanians from accessing these opportunities. Based on the interviews with TVET centers and the price information available online, the fees for technical/vocational courses range from JOD 300 to 1,750. Training topic, duration, official certification, center reputation, number of trainees, among other factors, determine the final cost of the TVET. However, it is important to note that the majority of TVET and skills institutions tailor their educational offerings based on the needs and resources of interested parties, i.e., two students doing the same training in the same institution may pay different prices. Individuals have weak negotiation power before TVET centers, but the private sector, public institutions and NGOs have the capacity to negotiate lower fees, as they can bring a large number of potential students.

⁷⁷ Valid identification document means ID card, birth certificate, residence permit, marriage certificate, driving license, passport, work permit, family book and other related documents.

**Table 4: Fees of private TVET and skills institutions operating in Jordan
(expressed in JOD)**

Technical and vocational training	Institution I	Institution II	Institution III	Institution IV	Institution V	Institution VI	Institution VII
Beauty and Cosmetics	1,250	900	680	750	310	500	N/A
IT	1,250	350	N/A	N/A	N/A	500	N/A
Administration & Management	750	1,100	N/A	N/A	N/A	250	N/A
Social Work	1,750	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	1,500	1,000

The room for negotiation is a necessary consequence of the second challenge related to the fees: **transparency**. Besides affordability, there is a widespread lack of transparency among TVET centers regarding service costs. With a few exceptions, the vast majority of technical and vocational training institutions do not publicly share their fees, forcing the interested parties to ask for a tailored offer.

Due to the prohibitive TVET fees, FGDs participants agreed that the only way to take part in costly TVET and skills courses was through **scholarships**, mainly granted by UN agencies, donors and INGOs. Although some of them expressed that they benefited from a TVET/Skills grant in the past, Yemeni, Somali and Sudanese AS/R unanimously complained about the lack of TVET and skills scholarships available for their communities. They have the perception that all education opportunities, including TVET and skills, funded by the international donor-aid community and the GoJ are addressed to Syrian refugees, feeling they have been left behind.

Furthermore, as JRS has stated, alongside the expansion of funding targeting these AS/R from both donors and the GoJ, a more practical approach to tackle the issue of excessively high fees in TVET is needed. This entails advocating for free and without documentation enrollment of all refugee jobseekers in technical and vocational training programs provided by the VTC and the NET, following the example of school students.⁷⁸

III.3 Acceptability of TVET and skills training

Acceptability of TVET and skills programs by refugees was analyzed according to three dimensions: **1) TVET and Skills preferences among refugees, 2) Quality of TVET, 3) Suitability of TVET for refugee needs and realities.**

III.3.1 TVET and skills preferences among refugees

The first analytical dimension of the acceptability of TVET by refugees is their TVET and skills preferences. As has been explained in the methodology section, at the beginning of each FGD, all potential beneficiaries filled in an individual questionnaire, which aimed to meet the first objective of this research.⁷⁹ Among the requested data, it was enquired about their personal information (including nationality and gender) and interest and experience on TVET and skills. This information allowed ARDD to identify TVET preferences among Yemeni, Somali, and Sudanese AS/R and disaggregate them by thematic areas, gender, and nationality.

A) TVET and skills preferences among refugees according to thematic areas

One of the questions formulated in the individual questionnaire distributed to the potential beneficiaries was: “Are you currently interested in receiving training?” and the following TVET thematic areas were provided: 1. Administration and Management, 2. Computers and Electronics, 3. Fine Arts, 4. Foreign Language, 5. Mechanical, 6. Clerical, 7. Customer and Personal Service, 8. Therapy and Social Work, 9. Beauty and Cosmetics, 10. Teaching, 11. Technical Design, 12. Construction and Building, 13. Cooking and Catering, 14. Environment and Agriculture.

⁷⁸ SRD Center, “Jordanians and Non-Jordanians Struggling for Decent Work: Labour Market Analysis of Amman and Ma’an Governorates” (Amman: JRS, 2022), p. 44, <https://reliefweb.int/report/jordan/jordanians-and-non-jordanians-struggling-decent-work-labour-market-analysis-amman-and-maan-governorates>

⁷⁹ “1. Providing background information for the purpose of facilitating the matching of selected beneficiaries, aged 18 to 28 from Yemeni, Somali, and Sudanese refugee communities in Jordan (and vulnerable Jordanians), with technical and vocational / skills training to enhance their livelihood opportunities.”

The top preferences shown by FGD participants in the questionnaire were **a) Computers and Electronics** and **b) Foreign Languages**. In comparison with the region, the information and communication technology sector in Jordan is progressively growing, being one of the main engines of the national economy. In 2022, it accounted for 3.8 % of the national gross GDP⁸⁰, hence the sector needs qualified workers. Furthermore, the demand for qualified professionals in such sector is amongst the highest outside of Jordan as well. People can work remotely for foreign companies without jeopardizing their legal situation in Jordan, or look for job opportunities abroad, accelerating a possible resettlement process.

With regards to foreign languages, both Jordanian and Yemeni, Somali and Sudanese AS/R are eager to learn English or other foreign languages for several reasons: **i)** speaking more than one language increases a worker’s competitiveness on the job market, **ii)** learning English (or any other foreign language) increases the chances of finding a job abroad, thereby constituting the starting point of resettlement in the case of refugees, and **iii)** Jordan is a humanitarian hub in the MENA region due to its stability, hosting a large number of INGOs, UN agencies, international organizations and other humanitarian actors, which generally provide better working conditions than the public and private sectors, but English speaking and writing skills are a must for any job position.

On the contrary, **a) teaching** and **b) environment and agriculture** were the least preferred options. For Jordanians, teaching, although it is mostly perceived as a high-medium-status job⁸¹, was not a TVET preference given that education is an academic field rather than a vocational one. In fact, no TVET on teaching was found during the TVET and skills providers mapping, either in the public or private sectors. Regarding environment and agriculture skills, unlike Syrian refugees who live in northern rural governorates of Jordan (Irbid, Jerash, Ajloun, Al Mafraq), 78% of Yemeni, Somali, and Sudanese AS/R live in Amman and their urban suburbs.⁸² Therefore, a TVET on environment and agriculture would barely increase their livelihood opportunities.

b) TVET and skills preferences among refugees according to gender

TVET preferences among Yemeni, Somali and Sudanese AS/R are shaped by **gender issues**. Firstly, it should be noted that the sample consisted of twice as many men as women (17 male participants compared to 9 female participants). The weak interest in vocational training opportunities shown by women is directly related to their poor participation in the Jordanian labor market. Jordan has one of the world’s lowest female labor force participation rates: in 2022, only 14.2% of women in Jordan were working.⁸³ Societal and cultural factors, the legal framework and sexual harassment are some of the main barriers preventing women in Jordan from working.⁸⁴

80 <https://www.trade.gov/country-commercial-guides/jordan-information-and-communication-technology>
 81 The national perception of the teaching profession in Jordan (2022 survey), <https://jordankmportal.com/resources/the-national-perception-of-teaching-profession-in-jordan-2022-survey-infographic>
 82 <https://data2.unhcr.org/en/documents/details/101162>
 83 GIZ & UN Women, *COVID-19 and women’s labour force participation in Jordan: A look into women’s labour force participation through the lens of the pandemic* (2022), 17. https://mol.gov.jo/ebv4.0/root_storage/ar/eb_list_page/2022_10_18_study_on_covid_19_impact_on_women_economic_participation_final.pdf
 84 ARDD, *Rising to the Challenges of Unemployment Among Jordanian Youth: Facts, lessons learned and recommendations* (2023), <https://ardd-jo.org/publication/youth-unemployment-in-jordan-failed-strategies-and-deferred-promises/>

Between the 14 work areas examined, Yemeni, Somali and Sudanese men preferred work and training in **a)** mechanics, **b)** construction and building, **c)** customer and personal service, **d)** technical design and **e)** Administration & Management (including clerical). Regarding professional categories **a)** and **b)**, it is noteworthy to mention that they consist of blue-collar jobs which, due to gender stereotypes, have been traditionally associated to male workers rather than women. On the other hand, **c)** is a working field where workers are dealing permanently with unknown people; hence, taking into account cultural norms and sexual harassment episodes or the fear thereof, it is widely accepted for men, but not women.

As for Yemeni, Somali and Sudanese women, **a)** therapy and social work, and **b)** beauty and cosmetics are the most demanded TVET programs. The female preference for social work is closely related to the gender biased perception of women as caregivers. Additionally, being a social worker is widely accepted for women in Jordan and the Arab world. Secondly, beauty and cosmetics are fields traditionally linked to women due to long standing gender stereotypes by which women must take care of their appearance according to beauty standards. This cultural and societal situation has led them to master these working areas.

According to the sample data, IT, cooking and catering, and foreign languages interest both men and women interviewees from the Yemeni, Somali and Sudanese communities, with male prevalence over females.

Gender stereotypes still play a key role among youth in Jordan in terms of TVET selection, specifically, in the Yemeni AS/R community. As mentioned in the methodology section, FGD participants were requested to fill in a self-skills assessment. In the technical skills-self assessment, some of the professional sectors examined were **1)** beauty and cosmetics, and **2)** mechanics. Some Yemeni women denied filling in their level of skills on mechanics, arguing it is a working field reserved for men. Yemeni men had similar thoughts about them working in beauty-and-cosmetics-related jobs.

A) TVET and skills preferences among refugees according to nationality

If TVET preferences are analyzed through a nationality lens, it could be concluded that IT, fine arts, and cooking are cross-cutting training fields among all the involved nationalities. Regarding the remaining professional sectors, Yemenis are more willing to conduct technical design and beauty training, and have a great interest in foreign languages, social work and mechanics; however, Somalis are more interested in administration and management (including clerical), construction and mechanics. In the small sample conducted, Sudanese did not seem to have clear preferences.

III.3.2 Quality of TVET

The second dimension of the acceptability of TVET by refugees analyzed is the quality of TVET from their point of view as a consumer/student. As has been already highlighted, TVET in Jordan suffers from a poor social perception and the quality of TVET is one of the reasons why. The lack of qualified and experienced trainers, outdated facilities with old-fashioned equipment, teaching methodologies focused on theory rather than hands-on learning, no labor market-oriented TVET curricula and other factors (See Section II.3) underlies the poor quality of TVET in Jordan.

Similar conclusions have been reached by donors, UNESCO, and other educational entities. *But, what AS/R, particularly, Yemeni, Somali and Sudanese, think about TVET quality in Jordan?* Acknowledging that ARDD’s scholarship program only covers 15 students on a single TVET provider and may not be the case for other TVET providers and students, these are opinions and views from the beneficiaries regarding their TVET/skills experience at KUTC (drawn from the base line and end line surveys conducted by ARDD):

- **Teachers:** Students rated KUTC teachers as highly professional, not only because they were experts in their fields, but also for their pedagogical skills. Moreover, students affirmed that some teachers were very supportive and inspiring, empowering them before any personal and professional challenge.
- **Classmates:** ARDD-VHI TVET/skills scholarship beneficiaries reported to have established extremely positive relationship with their peers, using the terms “friends” and “family” to describe them.
- **Staff and other students:** The relationship between the beneficiaries with KUTC staff and other students was based on mutual respect throughout the TVET/Skills scholarship. No episode of racism or discrimination against the youth was ever raised, allowing them to pursue their studies in a safe educational environment.
- **Facilities & equipment:** The majority of the beneficiaries consider KUTC facilities and equipment adequate and up to date to the Jordanian labor market realities. Only two students had objections about the equipment and facilities of KUTC: One mentioned that the equipment was antiquated according to his experience, and the other one thought that the materials delivered by the institution were not enough to meet the training requirements.
- **Curricula:** The 3-month TVET/Skills program at KUTC was divided into two parts: a common module on entrepreneurship skills, and the specifics of each TVET thematic area. The soft skills module was particularly appreciated among the beneficiaries. Refugee students emphasized the need to teach a minimum level of English in all TVET and skills programs, given that they always keep in mind resettlement as the preferred durable solution. KUTC has taken this feedback on board and provided free English courses tailored to the individual proficiency levels of 15 beneficiaries.

III.3.3 Suitability of TVET for refugees' needs and realities

The third dimension examined concerning the acceptability of TVET by refugees is the **suitability of TVET/Skills programs for AS/R's needs and realities**.

Similarly, to the quality of TVET, AS/R beneficiaries were asked, through baseline and end-line surveys, about if/how suitable KUTC and their TVET/Skills programs were for their particular needs and realities:

- **Legal documentation:** In order to enroll in the TVET/Skills programs, KUTC only requested the beneficiaries a valid or outdated identification document, whether their national passport or the UNHCR refugee card. No additional documentation was solicited. This flexible legal documentation policy makes KUTC a suitable TVET/Skills provider for AS/R from a legal point of view.
- **Affordability:** ARDD and VHI, with the financial support of the BMZ, were able to cover all the tuition fees for the 15 beneficiaries. In addition, a transportation allowance was delivered to each beneficiary at the beginning of each month, covering direct and indirect costs.
- **TVET field matched:** All beneficiaries expressed satisfaction with the TVET/Skills field matched by ARDD Program Department, based on the recommendations from the ARDD Research Department. Only one beneficiary complained about the TVET/Skills program matched for him, as he was not able to follow the lectures due to a language barrier (he did not speak Arabic well) and health issues (he was allergic to certain chemical products and materials used during the practical lectures). Therefore, at the request of ARDD, KUTC showed its flexibility by allowing this student to undertake another TVET/Skills program in a different thematic area and in English.
- **Duration:** As has been mentioned before, students benefited from a three-month scholarship (8th October 2023 – 11th January 2024). While some beneficiaries agreed with the duration of their TVET/Skills programs, others felt that three months programs were not enough to meet their educational needs, recommending extending the scholarship to at least one year.
- **Schedule:** With the exception of the common module on entrepreneurship, beneficiaries were going to KUTC 3 to 4 days per week, and with different schedules depending on their TVET/Skills programs (mainly morning to early afternoon). Some students raised it that was very challenging sometimes to combine this training opportunity with previous family and/or professional commitments. Hence, much flexibility in this sense should be given.
- **Transportation:** A high number of the beneficiaries live in the neighborhood of Jabal Amman and the KUTC center where they have been conducting their TVET/Skills training is located in the neighborhood of Tlaa Al-Ali, requiring complex and long journeys for those using public transportation means. Although ARDD provided them with generous transportation allowance, beneficiaries reported that they would have preferred a TVET/Skills providers nearer to their communities.
- **Job placement:** At the end of the TVET/Skills programs, KUTC provided one month of internship opportunities inside the college (including a transportation allowance) to the 12 beneficiaries, of which 6 beneficiaries took it. After the internship period, one of these 6 interns was eventually hired at KUTC. The remaining students apologized due to other professional or personal commitments. Furthermore, KUTC is committed to support all students in their search for job opportunities or internships outside the college through their professional networks.

Section IV

Key learnings

As a result of this research process, ARDD has extracted the following key learning with regard to TVET and skills, and Yemeni, Somali, and Sudanese AS/R (most of them applicable to Syrian AS/R), classified into four different categories:

A) Refugees as TVET students

1. Learning is an individual process. The learning journey is unique to each individual because students do not all engage with the same content and skills in the same way, nor do they share identical personal, familial, or socioeconomic circumstances.

By examining factors such as their financial situation, the balance they strike between training and other personal or professional commitments, and the support they receive from their families, a more comprehensive understanding of why students may thrive or encounter challenges in their learning journey can be achieved. Furthermore, learning is a dynamic process, involving a series of stages (such as acquisition, retention, application, and feedback) that students must navigate over time to acquire new skills and knowledge.

2. Motivation to enroll in a TVET/skills program can take many forms. In considering enrollment in a TVET or skills program, beneficiaries are motivated by various factors. A primary driver for applying for TVET/Skills scholarships was to enhance livelihood opportunities. Participants unanimously reported that participation in these programs had positively impacted their personal and professional growth by equipping them with new technical and soft skills, expanding their networks, and earning official certifications. Additionally, some students perceived TVET as a pathway to expedite their integration into the labor market, recognizing the demand for vocational and technical professions.

However, the pursuit of livelihood is not the sole motivation. Overall, participants viewed their TVET experience favorably because, as part of the matching process, they were trained in fields they were passionate about, aligning with their career aspirations. Whether refugees or not, individuals are unlikely to pursue training in professions lacking personal interest or motivation. Hence, it is imperative for TVET and skills providers, particularly NGOs, to customize opportunities according to students' preferences, avoiding imposition.

Moreover, the decision to pursue TVET may stem from it being the sole available alternative to traditional academic pathways. For instance, one beneficiary mentioned applying for the VHI-ARDD TVET/Skills scholarship due to the financial constraints of attending university as non-Jordanians.

3. Reasons for dropping out of the TVET/Skills training are related to both external and internal factors, some of them shared between beneficiaries. A distinction should be made between the reasoning for dropping out of pre-selected or initially selected beneficiaries, and final beneficiaries who eventually conduct the TVET Skills scholarship program:

- **Pre-selected or initially selected beneficiaries:** 11 out of 26 pre-selected or initially selected beneficiaries dropped out for one or a combination of the following reasons:⁸⁵ **a)** disagreement with or misunderstanding of the terms and conditions of the TVET/Skills scholarship contract with ARDD (2), **b)** schedule incompatibility with previous labor or educational commitments (1), **c)** finding a full-time job in the informal market (1), **d)** resettlement to a third country (3), **e)** unreachability after being pre-selected or selected (4), and **f)** fear of moving around Amman/Jordan without legal documentation (1).
- **Final beneficiaries:** 12 out of 15 beneficiaries successfully complete the TVET/ Skills program. 8 out of these 12 beneficiaries have been since the beginning of the research, showing their commitment to VHI-ARDD opportunity. The three beneficiaries who decided to drop out during the TVET/Skills program due to **a)** health issues (1), **b)** inability to balance the TVET/Skills program with a part-time job (1), and **c)** the TVET/Skills program did not meet their personal and professional expectations (1).⁸⁶ It should be noted that KUTC offered a supplementary course for these three students, two of them took the opportunity, but eventually they never attended it.

⁸⁵ (X) is the number of pre-selected or initially selected beneficiaries who mention x) reason to drop out of the TVET scholarship program.

⁸⁶ (X) is the number of final beneficiaries who mention x) reason to drop out of the TVET scholarship program.

As evidenced by the above findings, inflexibility on the part of TVET and skills providers emerges as a primary factor contributing to student dropout rates, as discussed in the following sub-section.

4. Transportation challenges can deter refugees from participating in TVET programs. KUTC was located quite far from the communities where these AS/R live in, which made it more difficult for them to balance the TVET/skills training with other professional and personal commitments. Moreover, it should be taken into account that some refugee students were reluctant to move away from their residential areas, as they lack valid legal documentation.

5. Refugee students consider soft skills as important as technical. From an end-user point of view, gaining only technical knowledge in a specific professional field is not enough for a successful school-to-work transition. They considered that TVET curricula must combine both technical and soft skills, particularly, English.

6. Refugee students highly valued the opportunity of paid work experience either during or at the end of their TVET/skills programs. After successfully completing their TVET/Skills programs, KTUC offered a paid internship to all the beneficiaries to meet internal institutional needs. Half of them took this income opportunity, applying the knowledge and skills learned. The remaining beneficiaries preferred to start looking for jobs or set up their own business in the TVET area where they have been trained.

7. Education programs for AS/R should benefit from including a protection dimension as part of their design and implementation. ARDD, on behalf of the 15 TVET/Skills scholarship beneficiaries, collectively negotiated with KUTC the terms and conditions of the TVET/Skills programs, ensuring that such programs were tailored to their educational needs and met their specificities as refugees. This approach allowed ARDD to provide them with a high-quality education program, while covering their protection needs.

B) TVET and skills programs

1. Flexibility is key to ensuring a successful learning journey. One of the biggest challenges pointed out by beneficiaries and other stakeholders for AS/R enrollment in TVET/Skills is the lack of / insufficient flexibility of TVET/Skills providers. Many AS/R students combine their training with professional and/or personal obligations, which sometimes can be very difficult to balance. Furthermore, TVET/Skills providers should understand that refugee students may be subject to random detentions by Jordanian authorities, rendering them unable to attend training sessions.

2. A three-month TVET and skills program was the minimum appropriate duration to provide new skills and knowledge to AS/R students. While the majority of beneficiaries believed that three months was reasonable and adequate duration for a TVET/Skills program, some of them suggested that this kind of training opportunity should last at least an academic year.

C) Environment

1. A safe and enabling learning environment is the result of a combination of elements. In terms of educational environment, what makes a successful learning journey is not an isolated factor, but a combination of all of them. For instance, teachers can be a determinant element in the learning process of a student, but he/she will not succeed or will be more challenging to do so if the infrastructure and equipment are not adequate, the classmates and staff are hostile to him/her, the curriculum is not updated and dynamic, etc.

2. Education fosters social cohesion among refugees of different nationalities, and between refugees and host communities. Some students shared that their relations with other project beneficiaries, Jordanians and non-Jordanians, have gone beyond the classrooms, establishing meaningful friendships thanks to the TVET/Skills opportunity. This positively contributes to enhancing social cohesion among these marginalized communities and between them and Jordanians.

3. Family and friends' support is crucial for students' educational performance. All beneficiaries reported that they were encouraged / had the sustained support of their relatives and friends throughout the TVET/Skills program, even if they had to leave their jobs to fully invest their time in their education. Overall, the parents of the students had a primary – secondary education level, which may explain why they are encouraging their sons and daughters to pursue a higher education attainment for having a better life.

4. Undertaking this TVET/Skills program has increased refugee students' social reputation *vis à vis* their families and communities. While Jordanians perceived TVET as a less attractive educational pathway due to its poor social image, AS/R are eager to enroll in TVET/Skills programs, having no stigma against vocational and technical stream.

5. Geopolitics affects but does not determine the learning journey of Yemeni, Sudanese and, Somali AS/R. The ongoing civil wars in Sudan (April 2023 - present), Yemen (September 2014 - Present), and Somalia (1991 - present), the unlawful aggression of Israel against Gaza (October 2023 - present), and other conflicts and humanitarian crises in the MENA region have had a direct impact on their personal lives of the Yemeni, Sudanese, and Somali students. Nevertheless, they stated that they have been able (or try) to focus on their TVET/Skills program. Therefore, it can be concluded that education has been used by the beneficiaries as a coping mechanism.

D) Durable solutions

1. Resettlement is the most preferred durable solution among refugees, and they believe TVET and skills opportunities can speed up this process. Without exception, all refugee students claimed that they would like to be resettled in a third country (USA, Canada, European countries) as soon as possible. They consider that doing technical and vocational training enhances their prospects of being resettled. Furthermore, they think these learnings could be transferable to the new country of resettlement, increasing their job opportunities there.

2. Self-reliance as a durable solution for refugees is not possible without inclusive labor market policies. Although their refugee condition was not a problem in enrolling and completing their TVET/Skills program, refugee students acknowledged that their legal status negatively affects their chances of finding a job in Jordan due to the current labor policies, particularly, the limited professional sectors open to non-Jordanians, the financial and administrative barriers to get a work permit to work in the formal sector, and the dilemma of having to choose between being registered within UNHCR or work legally.

SECTION V: The way forward

V.1 Key advocacy messages

- A strong and high-quality TVET system, from which refugees and Jordanians can benefit alike, is critical to enhance skills for the job market and increase the efficiency and productivity of the workforce, contributing to the economic and human development of Jordan.
- Even if livelihood opportunities are limited for non-Jordanians, skills and TVET education needs to be accessible to everyone in Jordan. For refugees, skills and education are critical tools for:
 - Accessing and/or obtaining resettlement opportunities in other countries.
 - Being productive residents in Jordan (as they can engage in economic activities sponsored online) or back in their country of origin, when the situation is safe for their return.
- For skills and TVET education to be accessible, particularly for refugees, they need to be:
 - Financially affordable both in public and private institutions (a system of grants for those who cannot afford it; establishing a transparent fee system for the private sector to enhance transparency and accountability of the education systems and avoid donor fatigue).
 - Legally accessible: documentation requirements should be waived or accommodate existing documentation.
 - Flexible and well-advertised programs and opportunities through NGOs and organizations providing services to refugees.
- Education and skills opportunities for refugees and host communities require adaptability to different personal backgrounds:
 - Some refugees and vulnerable Jordanians need integrated psychosocial support in order to successfully complete educational opportunities
 - As the level of disabilities is higher among refugees, this should be considered.
- CSOs play a critical role in service provision to host communities and refugees, particularly to marginalized refugees, such as Sudanese, Yemeni, and Somali.
- Collaborative efforts and synergies between all stakeholders including the public and private sectors, civil society, and TVET and skills Education providers are key to more inclusive opportunities in Jordan.

V.2 Recommendations

1. Recommendations for donors

- General TVET and skills recommendations:

- Strengthening the TVET system in Jordan should remain a priority. Areas that show success are on-the-job training opportunities, and enhancing skills intelligence: i.e. funding tracer studies to understand school-to-work transitions and quality education according to different sectors.
- Support CSOs and GoJ work to enhance public perceptions of skills and TVET education (technical and financial support).
- Reach and implement a common donor coordination strategy on the TVET sector in Jordan and identify (or create) a unique and centralized coordination mechanism for such purpose.

- Refugee specific recommendations:

- The protection dimension should be part of the design and implementation of any education program.
- Engage Jordanian authorities in conversations regarding enhancing access to livelihood opportunities for all refugees. Achievements related to the economic integration of Syrian refugees should be expanded to include all refugees.
- When providing funding to private institutions, encourage the practice of transparency regarding TVET fees by private institutions: educational fees should not be subject to speculation/ vary according to the contracting party.

2. Recommendations for CSOs

- General TVET and skills recommendations:

- Enhance public perceptions of skills and TVET education with public audiences through communication campaigns.
- Promote the vocational and technical stream among women (particularly, in male-dominant professional sectors) and persons with disabilities.

- Refugee specific recommendations:

- Improve referral systems between CSOs and TVET providers (public and private).
- Organize periodic information campaigns regarding TVET and skills opportunities for refugees and interested citizens.
- Engage with TVET and skills providers in offering complementary soft skills programs for refugees of different backgrounds that can help enhance the success of students registered.
- Consider the location of TVET/Skills providers where the refugee students will conduct their training. TVET/Skills providers offering their services to refugee students should ideally be situated in close proximity to their communities. In instances where this is not feasible, it is essential to provide adequate and timely transportation allowances or establish a private transportation system, such as a bus service with multiple pickup points. Despite the potential higher cost, a private transportation system not only fulfills its primary function of transporting students to and from TVET institutions but also mitigates the risk of sexual harassment for female students, thereby encouraging their participation in vocational and technical education programs.
- Provide TVET/Skills opportunities lasting from three months to one year.

3. Recommendations for the Private Sector

- General TVET and skills recommendations:

- Enhance on-the-job training opportunities for TVET and skills students.
- Support TVET institutions with up-to-date information regarding market needs of skills.

- Refugee Specific Recommendations:

- Engage in national conversations regarding livelihood opportunities in Jordan for non-Jordanians.

4. Recommendations for the GoJ

- General TVET and skills recommendations:

- Promote multistakeholder process/dialogue for recommendations regarding TVET supply (including curriculum review with a focus on soft skills), making TVET more labor market-oriented.
- Review the funding strategy of public TVET centers, investing more funds in teachers training, rehabilitation/modernization of public facilities and acquisition of new equipment. Tracer studies can support focusing on results.
- Promote private for public partnerships that can enhance results. Activities like tracer studies can support focusing on results.

- Enhance general public perceptions of Skills and TVET education with public audiences through communication campaigns.
- Swift implementation of the current TVET governance structure, including the activation of the work of the TVSDC and improving the coordination among all relevant stakeholders on TVET, particularly, MoL, MoE, NET, VTC and TVSDC.
- Re-visit the structure of the current education system for enhanced transition pathways, allowing the transition from the vocational/technical stream to the academic and *vice versa*.

- Refugee specific recommendations:

- Flexibility for refugees concerning **a)** documentation requirements, and **b)** age limits.
- Consider a system of grants for non-Jordanians to access public TVET and skills educational opportunities.

5. Recommendation for TVET and skills providers

- General TVET and skills recommendations:

- Further investment in career guidance and counseling for the students. Integrate student-centered pedagogical resources into the curriculum to enrich the professional development of teachers. This incorporation seeks to equip educators with innovative methodologies that prioritize student engagement and active learning, thus enriching the educational experience for students. .
- Enhance transparency regarding TVET fees by fixing standard rates and publicly disclosing them.
- Include in the TVET/Skills curriculum a paid work experience either during or at the end of the program, whether within the TVET/Skills provider itself (job placement) or externally (private and public companies). Ensuring paid work experience, such as internships or traineeships, at the end of the TVET/ Skills program would accelerate students' transition to the labor market. This allows them to put into practice their theoretical knowledge learned and acquire and consolidate soft skills, such as leadership, negotiation, and communication.

- Refugee specific recommendations:

- Foster a safe and enabling educational environment for refugees by zero tolerance towards discriminatory or racist acts, integrating them with Jordanian students, and considering their education needs and barriers (e.g., language).
- Further flexibility in two key areas:
 - Choice of professional field: TVET and skills providers must facilitate the possibility for students to change their selected professional field if they find themselves unable to pursue the TVET/ Skills training, whether due to health issues or other reasons. This adjustment should be made without imposing additional fees and should align with students' interests and abilities.
 - Schedule and attendance: Recognizing the challenges faced by refugee students who often have to juggle their training with professional and family responsibilities, TVET and skills providers should demonstrate flexibility in accommodating their unique circumstances. Therefore, TVET and skills providers should consider these factors when enforcing compulsory attendance requirements and designing the educational timetable, ensuring that they are reasonable and adaptable for AS/R students.

References

- Adaleh Center for Legal Information. "An amended system for work permit fees for non-Jordanians No. 3." In Official Gazette No. 5765, February 1, 2022.
- Al-Majali, Solenn. A Precarious Refuge: Yemeni Asylum-Seekers in Jordan. February 2022. <https://sanaacenter.org/publications/main-publications/16557>.
- Amala Education. "What is Amala?" n.d., <https://www.amalaeducation.org/what-is-amala>
- ARDD. "Documentation for Syrian Refugees in Jordan: Good Practices and Challenges." 2020, <https://ardd-jo.org/publication/documentation-for-syrian-refugees-in-jordan-good-practices-and-challenges-working-paper/>
- ARDD. "Rising to the Challenges of Unemployment Among Jordanian Youth: Facts, Lessons Learned, and Recommendations." 2023, <https://ardd-jo.org/publication/youth-unemployment-in-jordan-failed-strategies-and-deferred-promises/>
- British Council. "Inclusion of Refugees in Technical and Vocational Education and Training: self assessment tool." 2019, https://www.britishcouncil.org/sites/default/files/refugees_tvvet_self-assessment_toolkit_0.pdf
- Economic Empowerment Working Group - Jordan. "Operational Data Portal." October 2023, https://data.unhcr.org/en/search?type%5B0%5D=document&working_group=49§or_json=%7B%220%22-%20%220%22%7D§or=0
- Ensour, Abdullah. "Education for Prosperity: Delivering Results. A National Strategy for Human Resource Development 2016-2025." 2016. <https://en.heac.org.jo/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/National-HRD-Strategy.pdf>
- ETF. "Local Skills in Jordan." 2021, <https://www.etf.europa.eu/en/news-and-events/news/local-skills-jordan>
- ETF. "National Qualifications Framework - Jordan." 2021, 5.
- ETF. "Quality Assurance in Vocational Education and Training in Jordan." April 2020, https://www.etf.europa.eu/sites/default/files/2021-01/quality_assurance_in_vet_jordan.pdf.
- European Training Foundation. "Skills Intelligence." n.d., <https://www.etf.europa.eu/en/what-we-do/skills-intelligence>
- GIZ, UN Women. "A Look into Women's Labour Force Participation Through the Lens of the Pandemic." 2022, https://mol.gov.jo/ebv4.0/root_storage/ar/eb_list_page/2022_10_18_study_on_covid_19_impact_on_women_economic_participation_final.pdf
- Global Compact on Refugees. 26. 2018. <https://globalcompactrefugees.org/sites/default/files/2019-12/Globa%20compact%20on%20refugees%20EN.pdf>.
- Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan. "Constitution of the Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan." 1952, art. 21(i).
- Higher Population Council. "Empowering the Employment, Vocational, and Technical Education and Training Sector." 2015, https://www.hpc.org.jo/sites/default/files/Technical%20education%20training-Policy%20brief_0.pdf
- Human Rights Watch. "Jordan: Yemeni Asylum-Seekers Deported." Human Rights Watch, March 30, 2021. <https://www.hrw.org/news/2021/03/30/jordan-yemeni-asylum-seekers-deported>.
- Japan Official Development Service, UNDP. "Labour Market: The Case of Vocational Training in Jordan ." 2014, <https://www.undp.org/sites/g/files/zskgke326/files/migration/jo/Vocational-Training-Study---Final-Draft-presented-in-the-press-conference.pdf>
- Johnston, Rochelle, Final Baslan, and Anna Kvittinge. "Realizing the Rights of Asylum Seekers and Refugees in Jordan from Countries Other Than Syria with a Focus on Yemenis and Sudanese." April 2019, <https://rb.gy/r8xyon>.
- Kidd, Jennifer M. "The Career Counseling Interview." In *Rethinking Careers, Education, and Guidance: Theory, Policy, and Practice*, edited by A.G. Watts, B. Law, J. Killeen, Jennifer M. Kidd, and R. Hawthorn, 189-209. London: Routledge, 1996.
- Ministry of Labor - Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan. "Index of Appendices." n.d., https://www.mol.gov.jo/EBV4.0/Root_Storage/AR/EB_Info_Page/%D9%85%D9%84%D8%A7%D8%AD%D9%82%D8%A7%D9%84%D9%88%D8%AB%D9%8A%D9%82%D8%A9%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%AA%D8%AC%D9%85%D9%8A%D8%B9%D9%8A%D8%A9.pdf
- Ministry of Labor - Hashemite Kingdom of Jordan. "Syrian Labor," n.d. https://mol.gov.jo/EN/Pages/Syrian_Labor.

- Mixed Migration Center. “Displaced Minorities Part 1: Migration and Displacement Trends of Somali, Sudanese, and Yemeni Refugees and other Migrants in Jordan.” April 2017, <https://reliefweb.int/report/jordan/displaced-minorities-part-i-migration-and-displacement-trends-somali-sudanese-and>
- National Careers Service. “Discover Your Skills and Careers.” n.d., <https://nationalcareers.service.gov.uk/discover-your-skills-and-careers/>
- Ministry of Planning and International Cooperation, Ministry of Labor. “National Employment Strategy 2011-2020.” 2011, https://www.ilo.org/static/english/emplab/download/nep/jordan/jordan_national_employment_policy_2011.pdf
- OHCHR. “Report of the Working Group on the Universal Periodic Review - Jordan, Addendum 1: A/HRC/40/10/Add.1.” November 3, 2019.
- One Refugee Approach Working Group & Advisory Committee. “Education Barriers in Jordan for Non-Syrian Refugees.” n.d., <https://data.unhcr.org/en/documents/download/86982>
- SRD Center. “Jordanians and Non-Jordanians Struggling for Decent Work: Labour Market Analysis of Amman and Ma’an Governorates.” Jesuit Refugee Services, 2022, <https://reliefweb.int/report/jordan/jordanians-and-non-jordanians-struggling-decent-work-labour-market-analysis-amman-and-maan-governorate>
- Technical Vocational and Developmental Skills Commission. “National TVET Strategy 2023 - 2027.” n.d. , <https://tvsvc.gov.jo/wp-content/uploads/2023/12/National-TVET-Strategy-Final-EN.pdf>
- UNESCO. “Tracer Study of Tourism-and-Hospitality Vocational Secondary Education in Jordan.” 2019, <https://jordan.un.org/sites/default/files/2021-09/English%20Tracer%20Study%20of%20Tourism-and-Hospitality%20Vocational%20Secondary%20Education%20in%20Jordan.pdf>
- UNESCO & MoE. “Jordan TVET System Review. 2023 Technical and Vocational Education and Training.” (Unpublished).
- UNEVOC, UNESCO. “TVET Country Profile: Jordan.” 2019, <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000373090>.
- UNHCR, Working in Jordan, <https://help.unhcr.org/jordan/en/helpful-services-unhcr/working-in-jordan/>
- UNHCR. “Registered Refugees and Asylum Seekers in Jordan (as of 31 December 2023).” January 2024, <https://reliefweb.int/report/jordan/registered-refugees-and-asylum-seekers-jordan-31-december-2023>.
- UNHCR. “Statistical Report o UNHCR Registered Refugees and Asylum-Seekers Jordan as of 31 May 2023.” 2023, <https://data.unhcr.org/en/documents/details/101162>
- UNHCR. “Vulnerability Assessment Framework: Population Survey of Refugees Living in Host Communities - Jordan.” 2022, <https://data.unhcr.org/en/documents/details/93754>
- UNICEF. “Jordan Commits to Provide Education to Every Child.” August 22, 2016. <https://reliefweb.int/report/jordan/jordan-commits-provide-education-every-child>
- United States Department of Commerce International Trade Administration. “Jordan – Country Commercial Guide.” Last Updated 2024, <https://www.trade.gov/country-commercial-guides/jordan-information-and-communication-technology>
- USAID. “The National Perception of Teaching Profession in Jordan.” 2022, <https://jordankmportal.com/resources/the-national-perception-of-teaching-profession-in-jordan-2022-survey-infographic>.
- Vocational Training Center. “Strategic Plan 2020-2022.” n.d., https://vtc.gov.jo/ebv4.0/root_storage/en/eb_list_page/strategic_plan_2020.pdf
- Vocational Training Corporation. “About Us.” n.d., https://vtc.gov.jo/En/Pages/About_Us
- UNDESA. “Ensure Inclusive and Equitable Quality Education and Promote Lifelong Learning Opportunities for All.” <https://sdgs.un.org/goals/goal4>. 2023.

Annex I: Donor mapping of TVET and skills funded projects for fostering livelihood for refugees in Jordan (2015 – 2025)

	Donor	Project Name	Duration (2015 -2025)
Government development aid agencies	Agence Française de développement	TAGHYR: Access to employment for Youth	2018 - 2022
		TANMYAH: Access to Vocational Training, Employment, and Development	2018 - 2023
		AMAL: Bringing Hope Through jobs for young Jordanian and Syrian Refugees	2018 - 2022
	Agenzia Italiana per la Cooperazione allo Sviluppo	Enhance the self-reliance and inclusion prospects of displaced-affected communities in Amman	2020 - 2022
		Towards a More Inclusive Economy through Immediate Job Generation and Enterprise Development for Vulnerable Refugee and Host Communities in Jordan	2020 - 2022
	Australia Aid	Syria crisis humanitarian and resilience package	2017 - 2019
		Decent Work in Jordan’s Floriculture Sector	2019 - 2021
		The School of Second Chances: Access to Reintegration through Learning Opportunities for Children Deprived of Liberty in Jordan	N/A
	European Union Delegation in Jordan / EU	Creating decent job opportunities through applying Employment Intensive Approaches at Cultural Heritage Conservation activities	2020 - 2023
		Syrian-Jordanian Education Programme	2015 - 2023
	FCDO	Jordan Labour Market Programme	2017 – 2021
		Developing skills in agriculture and construction sectors for economic growth in Jordan	2016 – 2017
		Supporting the strategic objectives of the London Syria Conference 2016	2016 – 2017
		Supporting the strategic objectives of the London Syria Conference 2016 (Phase II)	2017 – 2018
	German Development Bank (KfW)	Employment through Labour Intensive Infrastructure in Jordan	2016 – 2018
		Employment through Labour Intensive Infrastructure in Jordan (Phases II, III, IV, V)	2018 – 2021
	BMZ/GIZ	Orange Digital Centers: Digital Skills for Employment	2020 – 2022
		Vocational Training and Skill Enhancement for Jordanians and Syrian Refugees in the Water Sector	2016 – 2019
		Qualification oriented to employment in the craft	2017 – 2024
		Investing in the Future	2022 – 2024
Promotion of training to improve efficiency in the water and energy sector II in Jordan		2016 – 2019	

	Donor	Project Name	Duration (2015 -2025)
Government development aid agencies	Government of Finland	Women Economic Empowement	2015 – 2017
	Government of the Republic of Korea	Technical and Vocational Education and Training for Syrian and Jordanian Youth in Jordan	2016 – 2017
	Japan International Cooperation Agency	Economic Empowerment and Social Participation of PWDs	2017 – 2020
	Norway Ministry of Foreign Affairs	Job creation for Syrian refugees and Jordanian host communities through green works in agriculture and forestry (Phase I)	2016 – 2018
		Job creation for Syrian refugees and Jordanian host communities through green works in agriculture and forestry (Phase II)	2017 – 2018
	Dutch Ministry of Foreign Affairs	Improving Employment Opportunities	2016 – 2018
		Mehnnati - Challenge Fund for Youth Employment	N/A
		COOL – YA	2021 – 2024
		Youth-JO: Level UP!	2021 – 2024
		Souq Fann: Improving Economic Opportunities for Youth and Women Artisans in Jordan	2019 – 2022
		Alyusr Project for Sustainable Rural Women and Youth Empowerment	2018 – 2020
		Decent jobs for Jordanians and Syrian refugees in the manufacturing sector	2017 – 2019
		Advancing Decent Work in Jordan’s Agriculture Sector: A compliance model	2018 – 2019
		Womenomics as a Community Priority	2018 – 2020
	USAID	Youth Power Jordan Activity	2015 – 2022
		Youth with potential	2016 – 2020
		Training for employment activity	2018 – 2021
	US Department of State’s Bureau of Population, Refugees, and Migration	Formalizing Access to the Legal Labour Market Through Recognition of Prior Learning and Certification for Syrians and Jordanians Working in Construction, Confectionary and Garment Sectors	2017 – 2018
		Formalizing access to the legal labour market for refugees and host communities in Jordan (Phase II)	2018 – 2021
	Swedish International Development Cooperation Agency	Supporting a National Employment Strategy that works for Young Syrian Refugees in Jordan	2016 – 2018
Swiss Agency for Development and Cooperation	TVET in Hospitality	2022 – 2023	
	Social protection program towards improving resilience of refugees and vulnerable Jordanians	2023 – 2025	

	Donor	Project Name	Duration (2015 - 2025)
UN Agencies	UNICEF	Azem	N/A
		Youth Economic Empowerment	N/A
	UNHCR	Activating Livelihoods Referral Pathways Through Flexible and Responsive Coaching as Alternatives to Cash Assistance in Irbid and Mafraq municipalities	2018
		Strengthening Case Management of GBV CP in Amman and Activating Livelihoods Referral Pathways	2018
	WFP	Food Assistance for Assets	2017
		Food Assistance for Training	2017
Private donors	Yayasan Hasanah Foundation	Furthering Learning to Improve Life Chances for Students in Jordan	2019 – 2020
	Novo Nordisk Foundation	Resilient Youth, Socially and Economically	2020 – 2022
Partnerships	Chloé, EU, KfW, Government of Netherlands	Digital Skills for a Better Future	2019 - N/A
	EU, BMZ	Building the resilience of host communities and refugees in the countries bordering Syria	2016 – 2019
	BMZ, Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Netherlands	Trade for Employment	2017 – 2018
	BMZ, Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Netherlands, FCDO	Fulfilling the promise of the Jordan Compact: An integrated trade and employment proposal	2018 – 2020
	Kuwait Foundation of the Advancement of Science, GAC	Amaluna Youth Economic Engagement	2018 - N/A
	EU, GIZ, AECID	Qudra 2: Resilience for Refugees, IDPs, Returnees and Host Communities in response to the protracted Syrian and Iraqi Crises	2019 - 2024

